

23 November 2009

Renée Crain
Office of Polar Programs – Division of Arctic Sciences
National Science Foundation
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Ms. Crain:

Attached is the 3rd Annual Program Plan and Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885, between NSF and ARCUS. The report describes accomplishments for the period 1 January 2009 through present, expected activities from present-31 December 2009, and projected activities for 1 January 2010 through 31 December 2010, the third year of this agreement, with all necessary budget information and relevant appendices.

Included, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

1. A narrative summary of accomplishments, future plans, and discussion of major change in direction or pace, by individual task, including a timeline of activities and several appendices;
2. A one-page budget summary showing costs by five major tasks: Arctic Community Science Planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, Arctic Science Education, Information and Outreach, and Core Support (Schedule A);
3. A five-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for Year 1, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for 1 January 2010 – 31 December 2010 (Schedule B);
4. A one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire CA by Form 1030 categories, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for Year 1, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for 1 January 2010 – 31 December 2010 (Schedule C); and
5. The proposed budget and the request for **\$845,068** for the period of 1 January 2010 – 31 December 2010 on NSF Form 1030 (Schedule D).

The ARCUS Board of Directors and staff are very pleased with the achievements of the past year and the work we have accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact us.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Susan Fox".

Susan E. Fox, ARCUS Executive Director and Principal Investigator

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Helen V. Wiggins".

Helen V. Wiggins, ARCUS Director of Programs and Co-Principal Investigator

Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)
Providing Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program
Year 3 Program Plan and Progress Report of Cooperative Agreement
ARC-0618885

This document describes the program plan and progress report for ARCUS' five-year Cooperative Agreement, ARC-0618885, to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Division of Arctic Sciences to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education activities. This program plan and progress report summarizes, within each task and specific activity:

- Accomplishments for Year 2 (to-date) of the Cooperative Agreement (1 January 2009–present);
- Remaining activities planned for Year 2 (present–31 December 2009); and
- Planned activities for Year 3 (1 January–31 December 2010).

The budget report is included at the end of this document. The narrative organizes activities into four main task categories:

1. **Arctic Community Science Planning** – coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries; includes Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination, Arctic Data Coordination, and State of the Arctic Conference activities.
2. **Coordination Support for NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Programs** – specific coordination and support for the Division of Arctic Sciences programs; includes Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program Coordination, Arctic Natural Science Program Coordination, Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, and Arctic Section Science Materials.
3. **Arctic Science Education** – development and coordination of arctic-focused educational activities; includes Arctic Science Education Activities and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.
4. **Information and Outreach** – information and outreach activities; includes *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo mailing list, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Internet Media Archive, Arctic Community Outreach, and an Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) International Polar Year (IPY) report.

An additional fifth category is the provision of Core Support for ARCUS' NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects.

- Worked with J. Overland and H. Eicken to develop the workshop agenda: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/agenda.php.
- Provided partial venue support (catering costs only; the meeting room was provided by NSIDC).
- Organized meeting room logistics and communicated all logistics information to participants. Participants primarily provided their own travel support; some travel support was provided by NOAA; no participant travel support was provided by ARCUS.
- Supported one (1) Central Office/ARCUS staff (A. Loring) to attend in person; two (2) other ARCUS staff (H. Wiggins and B. Wade) joined via phone.
- Led discussion at the meeting on improvements in SIO format, web delivery, and outreach.
- Posted PowerPoints from the meeting online, with permission from the speakers: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/agenda.php.
- Completed and published meeting notes, which are posted as a PDF online at: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/index.php.

Planning and Implementation of the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook

Through discussions with the CIG, AG, the SEARCH Science Steering Committee, discussions as the 2009 retrospective workshop, and other community feedback, several improvements were incorporated into the 2009 effort, including the addition of regional outlook reports, more robust graphing, and a stronger education and outreach component.

All of the 2009 reports, the minimum announcement, and the final summary report have been released.

Specific accomplishments for the 2009 effort included:

- Created a Sea Ice Outlook electronic mailing list to provide a direct means for information dissemination and communication about the SIO. A subscription form is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/list.php>. There are currently 120 subscribers to the list.
- Launched the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook with announcements via ArcticInfo and a SIO email list (ArcticInfo announcement archived at: http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi_ai_getArcticInfo/4161).
- Completed several website updates and improvements, including: edited and updated content in preparation for the 2009 season, added “Regional Reports” area for regional-scale outlooks, added a “data links” page

(<http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/data.php>), archived the 2008 Outlook material

(http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2008_outlook/summary_report.php), prepared new templates for the monthly Outlook graphs, added an education and outreach section and resources, and reorganized the directory structure and improved navigation throughout the section.

- Worked with J. Overland and H. Eicken to edit, organize, and published online the June, July, and August monthly reports, including full pan-arctic reports, summaries, and regional reports. The August report is available at: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2009_outlook/report_august.php.
- Announced all reports via ArcticInfo, the SIO website, the SIO email list, and other relevant lists.
- Worked with J. Overland and H. Eicken to develop, finalize, and publish online the webpages announcing the 2009 September sea ice minimum, including comparisons to historical values and 2009 Outlook predictions, available at: www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2009_outlook/2009_minimum.php.
- Worked with J. Overland and H. Eicken to develop, finalize, and publish online the retrospective summary reports for both the pan-arctic and regional scales: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2009_outlook/2009_pan-arctic_summary.php.
- The Sea Ice Outlook was endorsed by the SEARCH SSC as an essential SEARCH activity, and endorsed by the IPY international office as a key IPY accomplishment.
- The Sea Ice Outlook has a significant following via the Internet. For the period 1 January–18 October, the Sea Ice Outlook website had 34,916 unique pageviews. Visitors hail from all over the world, with 60.6% from the Americas, 32.9% from Europe, and visitors from Oceania (3.5%), Asia (2.5%), and Africa (<1%).

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- **Community Meeting at AGU** – An open community meeting will be held at the fall AGU Meeting to provide an opportunity for the science community to add their perspective to what was learned from the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook, to offer suggestions for improvement for the 2010 Sea Ice Outlook, and to participate in the effort as a whole. ARCUS will lead organization of the meeting, including preparing announcements and materials, staffing, and follow-up.
- **Small (3-person) Planning Meeting for 2010 Regional Outlook** – Provide travel support for a small meeting with Hajo Eicken, Jim Overland, and Adriene Tivy (a post doc on leave from the Canadian Ice Service working with John Walsh on sea ice forecasting) to plan for a more integrated regional outlook in 2010.

- **Sea Ice Outlook Website** – Continue to publish content and activities on the SIO website.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

The Sea Ice Outlook effort is planned to continue for 2010 to provide a community-wide synthesis and monthly outlook on the state of the arctic sea ice throughout summer 2010, with an increased focus on improving the regional-scale Outlook. Specific activities will include:

- **Winter/Spring 2010 – Small Planning Workshop** – A small workshop (less than 20 people in Boulder or Seattle) will be convened to discuss the 2010 Outlook, with a specific focus on developing the regional outlook and discussing what observations are needed to support Outlook activities. Funds included in the CA include a small amount of catering costs and support for five (5) participants. Other participants are assumed to attend on their own funds, and we will work with other participating organizations (e.g., NOAA, NSIDC) to secure in-kind venue support.
- **2010 Outlook Reports** - Work with the SIO leads, J. Overland and H. Eicken, to edit, organize, and published online monthly reports, including pan-arctic reports, regional reports, and a minimum announcement.
- **Retrospective Analysis and Summary Activities** – Work with J. Overland and H. Eicken to coordinate, edit, and publish online a retrospective report. Hold an open community meeting at the fall 2010 AGU to provide an opportunity for the science community to add their perspective to what was learned in 2010 and plan for any future efforts.
- **Communications and Announcements** – Maintain the Sea Ice Outlook online mailing list to provide a direct means for information dissemination and communication about the SIO. A subscription form is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/list.php>. There are currently 120 subscribers to the list. Write and distribute relevant announcements to ArcticInfo.
- **Website** – Continue website updates and improvements, as needed.

1.1.B. SEARCH-ARCSS Integration Activities

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Worked with the ARCSS Committee, SEARCH SSC and Panels, and NSF to plan a merger of relevant ARCSS and SEARCH science planning activities, in the anticipation that NSF will no longer support the ARCSS Committee after 31 December 2009. As currently structured, the SEARCH and ARCSS Programs overlap in many areas of scientific focus—both programs focus on change in the Arctic and understanding the arctic system via inter- and multi-disciplinary approaches. This overlapping science focus has led to discussions in the community and with NSF regarding merging the science

planning process and organizational structure of the two programs. A new joint effort would reduce overlap and strengthen a shared community science planning process, while building on the intellectual pool and energy found in both communities. Specific accomplishments have included:

- Held approximately 30 calls and teleconferences with SEARCH representatives and the ARCSS Committee to discuss the ARCSS-SEARCH merge and possible approaches.
- Worked with ARCSS Committee chair, Josh Schimel, and the ARCSS Committee to create talking points for a meeting in D.C. in early March with J. Schimel, P. Schlosser, and NSF representatives.
- Worked with the ARCSS Committee to begin a draft document summarizing ARCSS Committee recommendations as discussions moved forward.
- Organized a teleconference held on Monday, 13 July 2009 to plan for a D.C. meeting and discuss the major issues involved in SEARCH-ARCSS integration. Participants of the teleconference included ARCUS staff, Peter Schlosser, Josh Schimel, Hajo Eicken, Matthew Sturm, Neil Swanberg, and Simon Stephenson. ARCUS developed and distributed the teleconference agenda items and discussion topics before the call, and followed up with organization and planning for an in-person meeting.
- Prepared, organized, and participated in an in-person meeting 15–16 September 2009 at NSF, to discuss next steps of the SEARCH-ARCSS merge. As follow-up to the meeting, drafted, circulated, and revised a “position statement” document summarizing the recommendations that emerged from the in-person meeting (see Appendix A). The main activity planned is creation of an Understanding task force, to be chaired by Josh Schimel and John Walsh, which will produce a white paper with recommendations on advancing an “Understanding Change” program. Supported travel for P. Schlosser, H. Eicken, H. Wiggins, and S. Fox to attend.
- Convened a teleconference with the ARCSS Committee on 4 November 2009 to discuss the proposed Understanding Change task force activities; the ARCSS Committee agreed to the proposed plan.
- The SEARCH SSC discussed the proposed plan at the SEARCH SSC Meeting, 5–6 November and agreed that it should move forward.
- ARCUS is currently working with Josh Schimel and John Walsh to implement Task Force activities. A teleconference is being scheduled for November with J. Schimel, J. Walsh, P. Schlosser and/or H. Eicken, and ARCUS to discuss recommendations for Task Force members.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue follow-up on SEARCH-ARCSS integration activities, including:

- Work with Josh Schimel and others to draft, iterate, and distribute via ArcticInfo a communication to the broader community.
- Work with the task force co-chairs to convene the task force; finalize the list of task force members by the end of 2009; schedule and organize 2–3 teleconferences.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

The SEARCH-ARCSS merge and resulting “Understanding Change” activities will be coordinated by ARCUS in accordance with best practices of community science planning management and a “competency-driven model” focused on achieving results that all parties define as a success. Metrics of success will be defined beforehand. The process will remain transparent and collaborative, with communications to the broader SEARCH and ARCSS communities at key milestones. Specific activities planned for 2010 include:

- **Understanding Change Task Force Support** – Support the Understanding Change Task Force to coordinate and plan Task Force activities, including organizing teleconferences, tracking and follow-up on specific tasks, developing draft documents, and other activities, as needed.
- **Winter 2010 Task Force Meeting** – Work with the task force to organize and convene a small initial meeting of the Task Force in early winter 2010 (perhaps January 2010) to plan Task Force activities and work on an outline of a draft white paper on advancing Understanding Change science. The staffing, travel, and venue support for this meeting is included in this CA budget.
- **Summer 2010 Understanding Change Workshop** – Work with the Task Force to organize and convene a larger workshop to develop the draft “Understanding Change” white paper. Staffing for this workshop is included in the CA budget. Any additional funds needed would be requested through a more specific supplement request, once more details of this workshop are known.
- **Understanding Change White Paper** – Work with the Task Force to produce the Understanding Change white paper, including editing, formatting, managing a community review process, finalizing, and distribution (primarily online with a small in-house printing). The drafting and community review is expected to occur in fall 2010, with the final release in December 2010.
- **Webpages** – Create and maintain a set of webpages, as part of the SEARCH website, with information on Task Force activities, timeline, and products.
- **Communications and Announcements** – Draft and distribute communications to the broader community (via ArcticInfo) on Task Force activities.

- Other activities, as needed.

1.1.C. Science Steering Committee (SSC) Meetings

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- **August SEARCH SSC eMeeting** – Organized, planned, and implemented a SEARCH SSC eMeeting on 19 August 2009. -To save on time, travel, and staff resources and costs, the August 2009 SEARCH SSC meeting was held via electronic means as an eMeeting (using Wimba software). Prepared agenda, presentation PowerPoint, made technical preparations, and communicated to the SSC and panels information on the eMeeting. The eMeeting was primarily an informational meeting on current activities and planning in SEARCH implementation and events. 30 participants attended the eMeeting, including SEARCH SSC members and SEARCH Panel members. Prepared meeting notes and action items, and circulated to meeting participants and NSF. The eMeeting agenda, PowerPoint presentation, participant list, and meeting notes are posted online on the meeting webpages at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2009/ssc/index.php>.
- **Plan and Organize November SSC In-Person Meeting** – Scheduled fall SSC in-person meeting, which was held 5–6 November 2009 in Washington, D.C. Worked with SSC Chair (P. Schlosser), Incoming Chair (H. Eicken), SSC members, and NSF Program Director on an agenda and background materials. Created and maintained meeting webpages and content, including agenda, participant list, and posted presentations: http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2009/ssc_nov/agenda.php. Arranged all venue and travel support. Drafted and circulated meeting summary and action items (see Appendix B).

Remaining Activities for 2009

Follow-up for November SSC Meeting – Post to the website and announce final summary notes and action items, and post background materials. Follow-up and implement, in collaboration with P. Schlosser and H. Eicken, all action items that emerged from the meeting.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Plan and Implement 1–3 eMeetings and at least one (1) in-person meeting – Schedule, prepare, organize, and implement 1–3 SSC eMeetings and (1) in-person meeting. The schedule of the eMeeting and in-person meetings will be determined with the incoming SSC chair. If an additional in-person SSC meeting is required and not covered by a newly funded OPERA proposal, ARCUS will submit a supplement request to support any additional SSC meetings.

1.1.D. SEARCH Project Catalog

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

The SEARCH Project Catalog provides an easy-to-use, online, searchable means for the SEARCH organizational structure, agencies, and scientists to discover SEARCH implementation status and funded projects.

- Began work with the Understanding Change Panel (UCP), chair, J. Walsh, and the Observing Change Panel (OCP) chair, H. Eicken, to update the catalog with current funded SEARCH-relevant projects (including new AON awards, new ARCSS Seasonality awards, etc.), in order to assess the status of research addressing the SEARCH science questions; this activity is being undertaken in context of planning for AON Design and Implementation (ADI) activities.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue work with the UCP and OCP to update the SEARCH project catalog to enter funded SEARCH-relevant projects not already in the database, as needed.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Maintain the SEARCH project catalog to enter funded SEARCH-relevant projects, as needed.

1.1.E. SEARCH Interagency Meeting

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Discussed with H. Eicken and P. Schlosser a recommendation by the SEARCH Observing Change Panel for an interagency meeting to be held fall 2009, focused on coordination of arctic observing efforts. This activity will be accomplished as part of the fall AON PI Meeting and ADI workshop (see Item 1.1.F, below).

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

None planned.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

None planned.

1.1.F. AON Design and Implementation (ADI)

ADI activities, initiated through a proposal to NSF by H. Eicken and P. Schlosser, will develop an overarching concept that will guide the next, necessary step in design and implementation of the U.S. AON as part of a coordinated, international, multi-disciplinary, long-term Arctic Observing System (see Appendix C). An ADI Task Force will explore and evaluate different approaches and methodologies of potential use in system design.

The first year of ADI Activities include a combination of virtual and in-person meetings, two workshops and a small array of proof-of-concept or exploratory studies overseen by the Task Force, culminating in a summary report with recommendations for the next steps in optimizing, coordinating, and enhancing the existing components of an international arctic environmental observing system with emphasis on the AON.

ARCUS, as the SEARCH Project Office, will support the ADI process and ensure continuity and tie-in into the broader array of SEARCH activities and previously established recommendations and findings. This support will take the form of help in preparing workshop agendas, facilitation of ADI activities such as identification of potential contributors (including outside of arctic research community), compilation and organization of relevant documents and papers for workshops and associated work, and core support in assembling, producing and disseminating the final report.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Specific accomplishments to-date include:

- Discussed with H. Eicken and P. Schlosser the initial scope of ADI and AON meetings in fall 2009.
- Assisted the OCP in drafting the document "On the Implementation of an Arctic Observing Network in the Context of SEARCH and Other International Programs." Document was sent to NSF by H. Eicken as a discussion document and served as the basis for the final ADI proposal, which was submitted to NSF to initiate ADI activities and subsequently awarded.

- Worked with Hajo Eicken, John Walsh and Peter Schlosser to begin planning for an AON Design and Implementation (ADI) task force workshop to be held 2–4 December in conjunction with the AON Principal Investigators' meeting 30 November–2 December in Boulder, Colorado. The ADI workshop will address how the scientific community and others engaged in arctic environmental observations can best achieve a well-designed, effective, and robust arctic observing system. Discussions will focus on identifying promising approaches for exploratory studies to evaluate potential value of different observing approaches and methodologies and develop a work plan for the remainder of the ADI initiative. A task force is leading the ADI activities (task force members are listed at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/aon.html>).
- Helped organize, and participated in, a teleconference of the ADI task force, held on 18 September 2009. Participated in a teleconference of the task Force Executive Committee (a subset of the full task force: Hajo Eicken, chair; Sandy Andelman, Craig Lee, Peter Schlosser, John Walsh) on 5 October 2009.
- Began gathering background materials for the ADI workshop, identifying workshop participants, and issuing invitations.
- Participated in teleconference of the AON PI Meeting Organizing Committee on 2 September 2009 to support coordination of AON and ADI planning. The AON Organizing Committee members include: Craig Lee, chair; Donie Bret-Harte, Lisa Darby, Hajo Eicken, Larry Hamilton, Max Holmes, Jim Moore, Jill Reisdorf, Mary-Louise Timmermans, and Von Walden.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue planning for ADI workshop. Specific activities will include: organizing two (2) additional task force teleconferences and one (1) executive committee teleconference; attend AON PI meeting; assist the Task Force with agenda development, participant invitations, development of background materials, and posting website content. Participate in the AON PI Meeting and ADI workshop to provide meeting support, take notes, and assist in follow-up activities.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue organizational support of ADI Task Force activities, as requested. Specific support activities will include:

- Scheduling and organizing ADI teleconferences, and support in compiling and distributing relevant documents and resources for Task Force work.
- Organizational support for a small ADI Task Force planning meeting in early 2010.
- Organizational and staff support for a spring 2010 ADI workshop.
- Support in assembling, producing, and disseminating the final report.

- Other organizational support activities, as needed. No participant travel support or venue costs for ADI or AON activities will be provided by ARCUS, as JOSS/NCAR will be providing logistics support through their role as the AON Cooperative Arctic Data and Information Service (CADIS).

1.1.G. Develop Online List of SEARCH-related Science Articles

In several community discussions, including with members of the SEARCH SSC, a need has been expressed for a way in which members of the research community can be kept apprised of recent peer-reviewed publications relevant to arctic environmental change. ARCUS proposes to initiate a modest effort to develop and maintain a simple online list of recent SEARCH-relevant science articles (bibliographic references only, not article content). This would be done through a monthly call for contributions via ArcticInfo; entries would be submitted through an online form and then published to a simple webpage. Such an activity would improve communication within the community on SEARCH-related science and would provide a valuable resource on the status and highlights of environmental arctic change science.

Accomplishments or Remaining Activities To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

None; activity not yet initiated.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Discuss activity further with SEARCH SSC Chair and SEARCH members and develop a detailed implementation plan for the activity.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Initiate activity, including creation of an online form and webpage, and monthly announcements to solicit bibliographic contributions.

1.1.H. Other SSC and Panel Support

Support SEARCH SSC and Panel activities, including organizing and planning teleconferences, development of relevant drafts and materials, website content development, and other support as needed.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Implemented nominations of new SSC members, with Hajo Eicken (UAF) as incoming SEARCH SSC Chair, and Uma Bhatt (UAF), Caspar Ammann, (NCAR), and Nate Mantua (U. of Washington) as nominees for SSC Members. Nominees were approved by the IPMC, via N. Swanberg, IPMC Chair, and members were invited. Eicken, Bhatt, and Ammann have accepted the invitations and have been participating in SSC activities.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- Work with incoming chair and SSC to nominate and appoint any new SSC members, as needed.
- Continue working with OCP and the Understanding Change Panel (UCP) on panel activities, as requested.
- Responding to Change panel membership and activities are on hold until such time that the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) responding white paper is developed, with input from SEARCH (expected spring 2010).

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Support SEARCH SSC and Panel activities, including organizing and planning teleconferences, development of relevant drafts and materials, website content development, and other support as needed.
- Work with SSC Chair, SSC, and IPMC to formulate needs and directions for the Responding to Change panel; reconvene panel and panel charge, as appropriate.

1.1.I. Coordination with Relevant International Efforts

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- Provided travel support for P. Schlosser, SSC Chair, to attend the Arctic Science Summit Week conference in March 2009 (<http://www.imr.no/assw2009/>) to present and discuss SEARCH activities and planning.
- Provided travel support for Matt Berman, UCP co-chair, for a SEARCHforDAMOCLES (S4D) workshop on "Modeling Coupled Social-Ecological Responses to Climate Variability and Change in Arctic Marine Systems," 14–15 September 2009 at CICERO in Oslo (workshop website at: http://www.oasys-research.de/S4D_Oslo_2009/background).
- Continued partnership activities with DAMOCLES, including facilitating participation of DAMOCLES in SEARCH activities (Sea Ice Outlook, State of the Arctic Conference).
- Discussed with P. Schlosser and M. Fortier creation of draft MOU between ArcticNet and SEARCH to coordinate science and outreach activities.
- Facilitated International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) coordination with SEARCH activities (Sea Ice Outlook, State of the Arctic Conference, updated ISAC links on SEARCH website).
- Provided travel support for five (5) U.S. SEARCH participants in the DAMOCLES General Assembly meeting 10–12 November 2009, focused on "The Arctic Climate

System, its Present Status, Future Evolution and Potential Impacts.” Participants to be supported are: Peter Schlosser, John Toole (WHOI), Ola Persson (CIRES), Ole Martin Smedstad (Naval Research Laboratory), and Wieslaw Maslowski (Naval Postgraduate School).

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

None planned.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Travel for five (5) SEARCH representative(s) to international collaboration meetings; specific travel requests will be discussed with the SEARCH SSC Chair and approval requested from N. Swanberg.
- Work with SSC and coordinate with ISAC on fostering international partnerships, including an MOU with ArcticNet, and discussions with other programs (e.g., SCANNET, SAON, etc.) as appropriate.

1.1.J. Other Travel Support for SSC Chair and/or Key SEARCH Representatives

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

No other travel support was needed.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Will process any travel support requests; no current travel requests are pending or expected.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Provide travel support to the SSC Chair and/or key SEARCH representatives (up to three) to key arctic meetings for invited SEARCH presentations and sessions, as appropriate.

1.1.K. SEARCH Website

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- Completed ongoing website content updates, maintenance, and development. Completed specific updates in the Sea Ice Outlook, meetings, SSC/panel, and science news sections.
- For the period 1 January–17 November, the SEARCH website had 59,287 page views.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- Continue content updates and maintenance, as needed, including creation of webpages for ADI activities and information related to the Understanding Task Force activities.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Ongoing website content updates, maintenance, and development, as needed.

1.1.L. Transition to OPERA-funded Activities

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

As appropriate given the timing and funded projects of OPERA, ARCUS will work with OPERA projects to transition any relevant activities, as needed.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

The results of the OPERA solicitation (successful awards likely announced summer 2010), and any subsequent changes to ARCUS activities as the current SEARCH Project Office, may represent a major change in direction and pace for 2010.

1.2 ARCTIC DATA COORDINATION

A clear need exists for improved arctic data coordination and management across disciplines, research programs, and agencies, with activities that capitalize on developments in cyberinfrastructure concepts and tools. ARCUS works to facilitate to improved data coordination approaches and collaborations.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Metadata for Arctic Observation Activities GIS Database – As proposed by ARCUS to facilitate data sharing, began development of core metadata for the Geographic Information System (GIS) of U.S. observing activities that was created for the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report “Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a US Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing.”

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- Finish development of basic metadata documentation for the GIS layers and produce a short final report of the project; final metadata report will be completed by end of 2009.
- When metadata is completed, GIS layers will be distributed to CADIS, ARMAP, and GINA; the availability of the GIS layers will be announced via ArcticInfo and other relevant lists.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

None planned.

1.3 STATE OF THE ARCTIC CONFERENCE

The State of the Arctic Conference will be held 16–19 March 2010 at the Hyatt Regency Miami in Miami, Florida. The main goal of the conference is to review our understanding of the arctic system in a time of human-induced, rapid environmental change.

The State of the Arctic Conference will provide an open international forum for discussion of future research directions aimed toward better understanding of the arctic system and its trajectory. Topics will range from basic understanding of the Arctic and system-wide change, to developing response strategies to adapt and mitigate change. Major science themes, which will be refined as planning moves forward, will include:

1. Advances in arctic system understanding - the basic functioning of the arctic system, including its human dimensions;
2. Arctic change - rapid, system-scale changes and the capability to project future states of the arctic system under various scenarios;
3. Linkages to the Earth system - linkages and feedbacks between the arctic system and the Earth system; and
4. Translating research into solutions - informed solutions to the problems caused by environmental change.

The conference was conceived and developed by the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) and the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program communities. Current partners include: the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC), the Canadian ArcticNet Network of Centres of Excellence, the European Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES) program, and the U.S. Arctic Research Commission (USARC). ARCUS is organizing the conference on behalf of the arctic community and sponsoring organizations.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Planning for State of the Arctic commenced in early 2009. Accomplishments to-date include:

1. *Conference Prospectus* – Worked with Peter Schlosser, Conference Chair, on initial conference prospectus to outline the background, development, and goals for the conference.
2. *Secured Venue* – Researched available venues and dates for conference. Discussions with NSF and the conference Executive Committee resulted in selection of the Hyatt Regency Miami, Miami Convention Center (<http://miamiregency.hyatt.com/hyatt/hotels/index.jsp>) for the week of 15 March 2010.

3. *Finalized Venue and Sleeping Room Contracts* – Negotiated and finalized contract with venue for meeting rooms and sleeping rooms, and completed a site visit of the venue in June 2009.
4. *Convened Executive Committee* – Convened a conference Executive Committee (EC) whose membership includes: Peter Schlosser (SEARCH SSC Chair), Hajo Eicken (Chair of OCP and incoming SEARCH SSC Chair), Martin Fortier (ArcticNet Executive Director), Jean-Claude Gascard (DAMOCLES), Maribeth Murray (ISAC Executive Director, member of SEARCH OCP, member of ARCSS Committee), Josh Schimel (ARCSS Committee Chair), and Helen Wiggins (ARCUS).
5. *Announced Conference* – Developed and circulated first announcement for the conference (see: <http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi ai getArcticInfo/4180>). The announcement was distributed via several listserves, including ArcticInfo, DAMOCLES, ISAC, ArcticNet, IASSA, IASC, IPY, and many others.
6. *Budget Planning* – Created an initial budget for all conference activities (for 2009 and 2010).
7. *Launched Website* – Designed layout, graphics, and content for a State of the Arctic website; iterated design and core content with the EC, OC, and NSF. Launched the website at: <http://soa.arcus.org>.
8. *Internal Planning Meetings* – Convened several (approximately bi-weekly) internal ARCUS meetings for conference planning.
9. *Convened Organizing Committee* – Worked with the Executive Committee to convene a multi-disciplinary Organizing Committee (OC) to lead the scientific content of the conference. The list of Organizing Committee members is available at: <http://soa.arcus.org/about/organizing-committee>.
10. *Convened Executive Committee Teleconferences* – Scheduled, organized, created materials and agendas, and convened ten (10) EC planning teleconferences on the following dates: 23 April, 30 April, 12 May, 15 June, 14 July, 23 July, 25 August, 10 September, 29 September, and 16 October; planning discussions are also ongoing via email. Distributed action items and meeting summaries after each call and followed-up on action items with EC members, as needed.
11. *Convened Organizing Committee Teleconferences* – Convened and planned three (3) full OC teleconferences on 28 July, 31 August, 9 October, and 26 October; scheduled teleconferences, drafted the teleconference agenda, prepared and distributed background materials, took notes, distributed meeting notes and action items, and followed-up with tasks, as needed.
12. *Developed Outreach Video* – Developed and posted online a short multi-media video for outreach purposes.
13. *Conference Program* – Worked with the Executive Committee on a draft program/agenda outline, as a starting document for comment and input by the OC. Iterated the draft program several times with the EC, OC and with input from NSF.

The program will include plenary sessions, parallel science sessions, and poster sessions, and will be focused on state-of-the-knowledge science themes. The conference will be organized as an approximately three-day meeting, with short keynote plenary sessions, a significant portion of parallel science sessions, and poster sessions. A fourth day will focus on international collaborations.

14. *Community Input* – Developed, launched, solicited, and tracked community input through an online form, to collect community ideas on conference themes, topics, structure, or other suggestions relevant to the conference program. Collated and distributed input to the OC to ensure key community ideas were incorporated in conference planning.
15. *Parallel Session Themes* – Worked with the Executive Committee on initial parallel session themes, and iterated themes with EC, OC, and SEARCH SSC members.
16. *Discussions with NSF* – Discussed conference planning with NSF program managers in person during an in-person meeting 15–16 September, and on various phone calls.
17. *Project Management Software* – Adopted “BaseCamp” project management software to track internal conference planning activities; provided access to NSF for communicating conference planning tasks.
18. *Launched Registration* – Developed and launched an online registration form and process, which is available at: <http://soa.arcus.org/register>.
19. *Launched Abstract Submission* – Developed and launched a comprehensive abstract submission process for poster and parallel sessions: <http://soa.arcus.org/abstracts>
20. *Media Planning Teleconference* – Held initial teleconference on 16 November 2009 with ARCUS, N. Swanberg, and NSF press contact Dana Cruikshank to discuss overall strategy for press involvement.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue State of the Arctic planning and implementation. Specific activities will include:

1. *Website*: Continue to maintain and develop the conference website, including posting and updating the conference program, registration, abstract submission, logistics information, partner and sponsorship information, latest news, community input form, and other relevant resources.
2. *Conference Outcomes and Products*: Work with the conference Organizing Committee to develop a detailed plan for expected outcomes and products. Work with the OC to ensure that the conference

outcomes are clearly defined and will serve to advance arctic science for the research community and funding agencies.

3. *Program Development*: Continue to work with the Organizing Committee and sponsoring/partner organizations to formulate the conference program to ensure conference objectives and outcomes are met.
4. *Executive Committee and Organizing Committee Coordination and Support*: Provide organizational and content support to the Organizing Committee and Executive Committee. Committee coordination activities will include: arranging and convening teleconferences; preparing and circulating draft documents; integrating committee input and perspectives into conference plans; and tracking milestones and action items.
5. *Community Input*: Track and manage broad community input for science themes and topics provided through the online community input form and through other means; work with the Organizing Committee to address input and suggestions, as appropriate, and communicate back to community members.
6. *Abstract Submission and Management*: Manage the online abstract submission process; work with the Organizing Committee to create and manage a process to select talks and posters; maintain preliminary abstract proceedings online via a searchable database, and publish final abstracts either online and/or in hardcopy.
7. *Speaker Recruitment and Invitations*: Work with the Organizing Committee to recruit and invite conference speakers for plenary and parallel sessions, and provide speakers with speaker guidelines to ensure all talks adhere to high-quality content and organizational expectations.
8. *Parallel/Break-Out Session Organization*: Work with the Organizing Committee to organize parallel or break-out science sessions, including selection of session chairs and development of session foci; work with selected session chairs to determine logistical needs; provide support to session chairs for session organization, including arranging session planning teleconferences, developing and circulating session materials, and other support as needed.
9. *Registration*: Develop, manage, and track on-line registration and maintain an up-to-date online participant list on the conference website. Registration will be announced along with publication of the initial online conference program in late October.
10. *Outreach and Announcements*: Distribute regular conference announcements via listserves and to key organizations and programs, with hardcopy announcements at select conferences and meetings.
11. *Press/Media Activities*: Work with the NSF and the Organizing Committee on a media outreach strategy and onsite press coverage to ensure significant national and international media coverage and public outreach. A Miami-area consultant, with expertise in media and conference outreach has been retained; a teleconference will

be scheduled with the consultant, ARCUS, and appropriate NSF staff (November target date).

12. *Student/Young Investigator Program*: Develop and administer a merit-based student/young investigator scholarship program to encourage the participation of young investigators, including participation of students local to the venue.
13. *Logistics*: Coordinate all logistical and technical requirements with conference center and hotels, including meeting room(s) set-up, catering, audio/visual needs, and sleeping room blocks.
14. *Travel Support*: Begin travel support arrangements for selected participants (e.g., keynote speakers).
15. *Side Meetings*: Coordinate scheduling for any associated “side meetings” requested by community groups; on-site side meeting staffing support will be kept at a minimal level.
16. *Co-Sponsorship*: Solicit agency and organizational co-sponsors, specifically those that are participants in the SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC) and/or the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC). Encourage co-sponsorship for select conference activities, including student/young investigator support.
17. *Offsite Field Trips*: Arrange and/or provide information on possible offsite “side trips” for meeting participants (e.g., dinner cruise, local science/nature attractions); participants would pay for any additional costs for side trips.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue conference planning, on-site conference organization and support, and post-meeting activities. Note that funding for the expected 2010 costs have already been awarded through a supplement request (as requested by NSF); these costs are included in the 2010 budget but are subtracted for the actual funding request. Specific activities in 2010, in addition to continuation of all of the above 2009 activities, include:

1. *Participant Meeting Materials*: Prepare and circulate all participant meeting materials, including the agenda, participant list, venue and travel information, preliminary abstracts, local attraction information, and other materials. Most of the materials will be available as online or digital documents, with select documents (e.g., final program) available as hardcopy at the meeting.
2. *Presentation Planning/Support*: Work with speakers to collect and test PowerPoints, load onto presentation computers, provide “best practice” guidance for PowerPoints, and publish on the website (with speaker permission).
3. *On-Site Conference Staff Support*: Manage all onsite conference activities and provide staff support, including registration, speaker support, catering and audio/visual needs, web-streaming and video, plenary and parallel session management, poster

sessions, press management, banquet/dinner activities, and general participant support.

4. *Post-Meeting Website Content/Meeting Archive*: Develop and publish post-meeting “archive” materials, including the final agenda, presentation and poster abstracts, PowerPoint presentations, video, participant list, media coverage, and other information, to create a comprehensive online record of meeting proceedings.
5. *Conference Proceedings and Products*: Work with the Organizing Committee and NSF to determine final conference products (e.g., abstracts proceedings, review paper(s), etc.); work with the Organizing Committee to draft and finalize conference product(s).
6. *Other/Miscellaneous*: Other tasks, as needed and as budget allows.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1.1. ARCSS COORDINATION

The Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program addresses the physical, chemical, biological, and social processes of the Arctic and how these arctic systems interact with the Earth as a whole, including changes in the arctic system and their global ramifications. ARCUS has provided community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF Arctic System Science Program and has served as the ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO). After 31 December 2009, the ARCSS Committee will be disbanded. Therefore, a minimal level of ARCSS activities are proposed for 2010 (maintaining website, lists of current projects, etc.). See the SEARCH section, above, for information and activities related to SEARCH-ARCSS integration.

2.1.1.A. ARCSS Committee Meetings

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

ARCUS has worked with the ARCSS Committee chair and Committee members to plan, organize, and implement ARCSS Committee teleconferences, primarily to discuss the merge of the SEARCH and ARCSS planning structures.

Specific activities have included the planning, organization, and implementation of four (4) ARCSS Committee (AC) teleconferences, on 11 February, 25 February, 14 April, and 4 November 2009, with several additional calls with the ARCSS Chair (Josh Schimel), as well as a large volume of email communications with the Committee. A small subaward was funded for time to the ARCSS Committee Chair devoted to leading ARCSS Committee activities. Discussions have been focused on SEARCH-ARCSS integration activities and have resulted in agreement on a plan forward for an “Understanding Change” task force.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue discussions with the ARCSS Committee regarding SEARCH-ARCSS merger and any activities needed to wrap-up final Committee activities, including a communication to the broad community. ARCUS will continue to support ARCSS Committee activities until 31 December 2009, when the ARCSS Committee will be dissolved with the formation of the Understanding Change Task Force.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

None planned.

2.1.1.B. HARC Subaward

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Funds continued from 2008 at the HARC Core Office at UAF have been used by HARC to develop a Synthesis Report summarizing ten years of HARC research, priorities for research (near, medium, and long-term), assessment of state of human dimensions research within arctic science, and a bibliography of HARC research publications. This document also will include a long-term vision/strategic plan to ensure continued and increased proposal pressure and to facilitate community awareness of opportunities for national, international, and interdisciplinary collaborative research and scholarly development in human dimensions research in the arctic.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

The final report is expected fall 2009, and will be distributed as an online report via the HARC website and relevant mailing lists, with a small printing of the Executive Summary.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

None planned.

2.1.1.C. ARCSS Website

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Minor updates to the ARCSS website, as needed.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Edit website content to reflect plans for discontinuing ARCSS Committee activities and launching of the Understanding Change task force.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue minimal updates of the ARCSS website, including links to any ARCSS Announcements of Opportunity, lists of funded ARCSS projects (e.g., Seasonality projects), or other relevant ARCSS-specific news.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

The discontinuation of the ARCSS Committee represents a major change in direction/pace for ARCSS activities.

2.2. ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

The Arctic Natural Sciences (ANS) Program is a multidisciplinary program within the NSF Division of Arctic Sciences that supports research in the atmospheric, biological, and earth sciences; glaciology; and oceanography. ARCUS will continue to coordinate ANS science planning activities related to the Bering Sea, a region that is ecologically diverse and economically and culturally important.

2.2.1. BERING SEA RESEARCH COORDINATION

Since March 2003, ARCUS has provided the Arctic Natural Sciences Program with organizational support and coordination of activities for the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) science planning process. BEST priorities for research were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Announcement of Opportunity (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2005/nsf05618/nsf05618.htm>) and in a special program solicitation in December 2006 (http://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf07533); awards through these opportunities were announced in July 2006 and September 2007. The funded BEST projects are the NSF contribution to a special research partnership with the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB) to support a comprehensive, vertically integrated investigation of the ecosystem of the eastern continental shelf of the Bering Sea.

2.2.1.A. Joint Science Advisory Board (SAB)

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

No activities to report in this period; the SAB has not held any in-person meetings.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

None planned.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Coordinate and support travel for three (3) BEST PIs to Washington, D.C. for the 2010 meeting of the SAB (dates TBD).

2.2.1.B. PI Meeting and Support

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- ARCUS staff (A. York) has participated in monthly PI teleconferences to remain abreast of program developments.
- Supported travel for one (1) ARCUS staff member (A. York) to the annual PI meeting, held 13–15 October 2009, to provide meeting support (<http://bsierp.nprb.org/meetings/index.html>).

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- ARCUS staff will continue to participate in monthly PI teleconferences and support any eMeetings, if requested.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- PI teleconferences and eMeetings – ARCUS staff will participate in monthly PI teleconferences to stay abreast of program developments. If requested by program leadership, support three (3) online eMeetings for research coordination and planning.
- Support travel for one (1) ARCUS staff member to the annual PI meeting in 2010 to provide meeting support.

2.2.1.C. Miscellaneous Travel Support

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- Supported travel for two (2) BEST PIs (E. Curchitser, Rutgers University and G. Gibson, UAF) to attend and present at the BEST-BSIERP Modeling Workshop in June 2009 in Seattle, Washington.
- Supported travel of Rodger Harvey to the Alaska Marine Science Symposium, Anchorage, 19-23 January 2009; to represent the BEST-BSIERP Science Advisory Board.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Provide travel support, if needed, to address program goals. No travel requests are pending.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Travel support to address program goals, as needed, for up to four (4) participants.

2.2.1.D. Development of an Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Plan for Beaufort and Chukchi Seas

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- ARCUS staff served on the organizing committee for the Arctic Research and Monitoring Workshop held 23 January 2009 in conjunction with the Alaska Marine Science Symposium. One (1) ARCUS Staff (A. York) attended the workshop. No workshop participant travel or logistics support was provided by ARCUS. This workshop was an initial step toward development of a comprehensive monitoring and assessment plan.
- The report from the workshop, *Arctic Research and Monitoring Workshop: Toward a Strategy for the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas*, has undergone public review (with editing and content input from ARCUS) and was released on 1 June 2009 (see ArcticInfo announcement at: http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi_ai_getArcticInfo/4177).

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

None; all planned activities completed.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

None planned.

2.2.1.E HBEST Science Plan

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

No activities to report in this period.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Editing and layout of the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan "*Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*," as a parallel plan to the BEST Science Plan. The HBEST Science Plan seeks to initiate research to elucidate the dynamic

relationship between humans and the Bering Sea ecosystem.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Final editing, online publication, and announcement of the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan “*Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan.*”

2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES COORDINATION

The Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP) is a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary program that encompasses all social sciences research supported by NSF. The Arctic Social Sciences Program supports research that documents and analyzes the dynamic cultures, economies, and technologies of northern populations.

2.3.1.A Reprint of *Earth is Faster Now*

The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change (2002), published by ARCUS in cooperation with the Arctic Studies Center, Smithsonian Institution, and compiled and edited by Igor Krupnik and Dyanna Jolly, is a collection of ten papers describing contemporary efforts to document indigenous knowledge of environmental change in the Arctic. This text has been an extremely popular resource and is now in low supply; a supplement was awarded to ARCUS to undertake a second reprint.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Worked with I. Krupnik to update the text with a new four-page preface and layout updates.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Complete editing and layout for reprint.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Finalize reprint and produce 500 copies.

2.4.1 NSF ARCTIC DIVISION SCIENCE MATERIALS

ARCUS, in collaboration with NSF program staff, will develop information and communication resources such as posters and brochures that reach across geographic, cultural, institutional, and disciplinary barriers to assist planning and integration of diverse research efforts and to improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

No activities to report in this period.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Work with the Renée Crain to update the *Arctic Discoveries* poster and/or Arctic Division brochure for use as an NSF outreach tool.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue and finalize update of Arctic Discoveries poster or other outreach resource, as determined by NSF.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

ARCUS will continue to provide an educational leadership role within the arctic community through activities designed to bridge arctic research and education.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- **Outdoor Days at UAF** – Participated in “Outdoor Days,” a three-day outdoor education program held 12–14 May for 6th graders, sponsored by the U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service and held annually in Fairbanks, AK. ARCUS hosted a "Climate Change in the Arctic" Earth Sciences station. The activity introduced students to carbon and the carbon cycle. Students were introduced to a variety of careers in climate change, and developed ideas for reducing their own carbon footprint. 630 students from 12 different schools attended, along with parents and teachers.
- **Extreme Cold Weather Gear Kit** – Collected and made available on request a kit of Extreme Cold Weather Gear for use in educating students and the public about the realities of polar research.
- **IPY Education eMeeting Planning** – Planned and implemented an IPY education eMeeting on 23 October 2009 to maintain the excitement of the IPY and to share and discuss the future of IPY legacy products. Participants included Principal

Investigators and other key personnel from US-based and NSF-funded IPY projects, and other relevant participants.

- *Provide Support for One (1) Science Teacher to Attend PolarTREC Orientation – This activity was not required as the selected teacher was unable to attend PolarTREC Orientation nor participate in an expedition.*

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- **ECW Kits** – Continue loaning ECW kits, as requested.
- **IPY Education eMeeting** – Continue follow-up to IPY eMeeting. In response to the IPY E-Meeting held this fall, ARCUS will illustrate the connections that have been established between the NSF-funded IPY projects during the International Polar Year. Using data collected via e-mail, the illustration will show connections between the 27 NSF-Funded IPY Education and Outreach projects as well as other projects involved in education and outreach during the IPY. This illustration will be part of the final report from the 2009 IPY Education and Outreach E-Meeting (expected early December).
- **Fall AGU** – Provide partial support for one (1) ARCUS staff to attend fall AGU to coordinate and participate in arctic education activities and sessions.
- **Other** – Other activities, as appropriate and as funding allows.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- **IPY E-Meeting Follow-up** – Follow-up, as appropriate, to recommendations resulting from the IPY e-meeting held in Fall 2009.
- **Outdoor Days 2010** (Mid-May 2010) – Participate in Outdoor Days 2010. Develop a global climate change/arctic related activity and organize the event onsite.
- **Extreme Cold Weather (ECW) Gear Kit** – Continue mailing ECW kits to teachers and the public as requested.
- **Educator Travel Scholarships** – Provide travel scholarships to support three (3) educators for collaborative education-research activities, including attendance at science meetings, workshops, or other relevant events.
- **IPY Weeks: Host PolarConnect Events** – IPY Weeks, an activity of the IPY International Office, are being created to sustain the excitement and momentum generated by the IPY Days during the International Polar Year. (http://www.ipy.org/index.php?option=com_k2&id=1113&view=item&Itemid=47). The IPY office has requested that ARCUS host, via online meeting software, 2–3 live events (to be scheduled). Specific activities will include: solicit presenters, compile slides, prepare agenda, arrange technology, coordinate registration, advertise for

participation, facilitate 1-2 hour event, and prepare and advertise archive of the event.

- **Staff Travel for Meetings/Presentations** – Travel support for two (2) ARCUS staff to attend a relevant conference. Potential meetings include the AGU Ocean Sciences Meeting, NSTA, the 2010 NOAA Teacher Research Experience Workshop, or fall 2010 AGU.
- **Greenland Education Tour Support** (Summer 2010) – Provide support, as determined by NSF (i.e. website, training, blog, photos, Greenland Symposium Live Event, other).
- **Polar Education Mailing List** – Maintain the ARCUS Polar Education List, which provides a venue for educators, researchers, and learners to exchange information about opportunities, challenges, methods, resources, important events, and other useful topics. The list is moderated but participatory so any subscribed user may post information or respond to posts.
- **Other** – Arctic science education and outreach activities, to be determined with the program officer, as opportunities arise.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents (see website at: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/index.html).

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- Supported one (1) AVS speaker this period, Michelle Ridgway, who visited the Alaska SeaLife Center in Seward (see: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/2009_tours.html).
- Updated AVS webpages and published several speaker profiles.
- Sent a call via ArcticInfo for AVS applications.
- Currently arranging two (2) tours:
 - Working with Chuck Kennicutt from Texas A&M to arrange a speaker to discuss an Alaska native worldview.
 - Initial planning for Donald Holly from Eastern Illinois University to host Orville Huntington in April 2010 to discuss the impacts of climate change on native communities.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue current program, with support for AVS tours as applications are received, up to five (5) total tours for the year.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue current program, but with a focus on “online” AVS tours.

- Continue in person tours, with support for six (6) tours.
- Launch new “online tours” (2), utilizing live Internet technology to bring arctic experts to audiences. The new online tours will be focused on specific science issues relevant to broad communities (e.g., an online tour featuring a scientist and local arctic community member discussing arctic sea ice).
- Update speakers bureau with new photos and bios, as appropriate.
- Outreach activities, including a call for researchers to join the speakers bureau and development of an online brochure that can be printed for outreach at appropriate meetings.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public.

4.1 *Witness the Arctic* Newsletter

Witness the Arctic is a newsletter that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

To improve timeliness of reporting and reduce printing and mailing costs, *Witness the Arctic* has changed to an online format, with shorter online news updates of interest to the arctic research community. Copies will be printed in-house only to send to key community members and to distribute at meetings, or as requested.

- **Completed and Distributed Winter 2008/09 Issue** – Completed, published, and distributed 15,000 copies of the winter *Witness* (Winter 2008/2009, Volume 13,

Number 1) in March 2009, the last hardcopy issue before the switch to online versions. This issue is a 24-page newsletter with a feature story by Mark Serreze of the National Snow and Ice Data Center. Published the online PDF version of the newsletter on ARCUS' website ([http://www.arcus.org/witness the arctic/winter 08 09/index.html](http://www.arcus.org/witness%20the%20arctic/winter%2008%2009/index.html)).

- **Developed Webpages for Delivering Online Format** – Designed and created online webpages for the new online format.
- **Completed Spring 2009 Issue** – Solicited and edited contributions for the first online-only Spring 2009 issue of *Witness* (Volume 13, Number 2). The feature story, authored by Mead Treadwell, highlighted the increased visibility brought to arctic issues by the accomplishments of the recently completed International Polar Year. Completed and released the Spring 2009 online issue on 29 May; the issue is available at: [http://www.arcus.org/witness the arctic/spring 09/index.html](http://www.arcus.org/witness%20the%20arctic/spring%2009/index.html). The spring issue webpages had 1,747 unique page views from its release to 18 October 2009.
- **Completed Fall 2009 Issue** – Solicited and edited contributions for the online Fall 2009 issue of *Witness* (Volume 13, Number 3). The feature story was “Coincidence and Contradiction in the Warming Boreal Forest” by Glenn Juday, UAF, a second article in an occasional series of authors invited to trace how their personal thinking about their research has changed over time. Completed and finalized the content and published online; announced its release on 15 October. The issue is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic/2009/3>. The fall issue webpages have had 447 unique page views from its release to 18 October.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- Solicit, edit, publish, and announce December “end-of-year” issue.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Continue development and publication of four (4) online issues of *Witness the Arctic*. The estimated publication schedule will be: March, June, Sept, and December.
- Continue to develop webpages and interface for an increasing dynamic, database-driven, and searchable content.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

With the Spring 2009, *Witness the Arctic* changed to an online-only format, which has resulted in significant cost savings in printing and mailing costs.

4.2 Website and Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves several thousand pages and files. The website is the focal point for educational programs, various community science planning efforts, and provides important information and resources to the research community about research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. The website provides program information; electronic copies of publications; agendas, abstracts, and participant lists from meetings, the online calendar, and other resources.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- Continued to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality. Increasingly used website-tracking software to analyze website use patterns, using Google analytics, and increased use of dynamic content.
- Since 1 January 2009, the ARCUS website has had 146,683 page views from 176 countries/territories.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue website updates and developments, with a specific focus on direct program needs.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue to develop/improve website, with a focus on increasing dynamic content, as appropriate for specific CA projects and programs.

4.3 ArcticInfo Mailing List

ARCUS continues to develop and maintain ArcticInfo, the primary electronic mailing list for the arctic research community. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other useful news. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website. Submissions and subscribers to ArcticInfo have increased steadily over the past years.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Continued to develop and maintain the mailing list, including receiving, editing, and

posting 467 announcements to the list to-date in 2009; ArcticInfo currently has 6,429 current email subscribers. We recently modified the format of the mailing list to include more than one announcement per email, in order to reduce the number of emails distributed per day. We have received positive feedback from our subscribers regarding this change.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue to develop and maintain the moderated listserv, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements to the list.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue to develop and maintain the moderated listserv, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements to the list.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to facilitate networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the Directory, which includes information on over 4,000 U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions (see website at: <http://www.arcus.org/researcher/index.html>).

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Continued to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers, which currently contains 4,139 individual entries.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Begin the annual Directory update of researcher's contact and expertise information.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Continue to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers.
- Improve Directory formatting for easier use. The Directory, originally planned for an annual printing, will be managed as an online-only resource, with improved viewing and printing capabilities for the end-user.
- Complete the annual 2010 Directory update of researcher's contact and expertise information.

- Distribute a call via ArcticInfo for new researchers to submit their information to the Directory.

4.5 Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of polar-relevant photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are shared through the ARCUS website at: <http://media.arcus.org>.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Continued to develop and maintain the IMA, including entering resources into the IMA database.

- 1,147 photos/graphics and 25 video/audio files were published to the IMA; 1,906 photos were added to the IMA database, and are in the process of being made public.
- Two (2) IMA “special collections” were developed:
 - (1) A “Climate Change” collection, featuring a collection of eight videos from various community workshops and meetings (<http://media.arcus.org/thumbnails.php?album=295>).
 - (2) A “Wildlife Response to Arctic Change” collection, featuring graphics from a US Fish and Wildlife workshop report (<http://media.arcus.org/thumbnails.php?album=282>).

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue to develop and maintain the IMA; organize one (1) additional “special collection” with commonly used sets of media (e.g., select photos of arctic landscapes, videos from meeting talks, etc.).

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- Continue to develop and maintain the IMA.
- Improve searchability functions and user tools for finding graphics, photos, and other media resources for various uses.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS continues to conduct a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

- **Arctic Forum 2008 Proceedings** - Finalized and printed proceedings of the *Arctic Forum 2008*, "Tipping Points—The Arctic and Global Change." The proceedings include presentation and poster abstracts, and summaries of panel, participant, and student discussions on priorities in arctic science and education. The volume was announced on 19 June, and is available online at:

http://www.arcus.org/annual_meetings/arctic_forum_archive/2008/index.html

Hardcopies were sent to AF participants and other key members of the community; the hardcopy versions were printed via digital rather than offset printing to reduce printing costs and represented significant savings.

- **2009 AAAS Arctic Science Conference** – Provided travel support for one (1) ARCUS staff to attend the 2009 AAAS Conference in Juneau, Alaska, to present and share information on SEARCH, State of the Arctic, and other ARCUS activities.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

- **Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall 2009 Meeting** - Provide and organize a "Community Meeting Space" at the Fall 2009 AGU Meeting to encourage scientific collaboration and to make face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. During the week of AGU, a small conference room (accommodating 20–30 people) will be reserved at the San Francisco Marriott, a location central to AGU sessions. This room will be available by appointment for groups working on arctic research or science education planning activities, with scheduling priority to groups directly related to NSF-funded programs. ARCUS has provided this space at AGU since 2005; feedback from users of the Community Meeting Space has been overwhelmingly positive, with many comments each year on the utility of the service to advance collaboration, networking, and enhance project outcomes.
- Other Community Outreach activities, as needed and as funding allows.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

- **Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall 2010 Meeting** – Provide and organize a "Community Meeting Space" at the Fall 2009 AGU Meeting.
- **Other Community Outreach** – outreach at AGU and other prominent arctic or related meetings and conferences, as appropriate.

4.7. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) International Polar Year (IPY) Report

As requested by Mike van Woert, OPP Executive Officer, ARCUS will assist with the completion of a special issue of Arctic Research of the U.S. (published by the NSF for the IARPC and the Arctic Research Commission) on the International Polar Year. Expected publication (online publication through NSF) is early 2010.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Discussed initial scope of work with Mike van Woert; reviewed draft content of issue; began report editing, with initial suggestions sent to NSF.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue to work with NSF to gather and synthesize information and graphics resources from federal agencies, revise text, and prepare layout for online publication.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue editing, coordinate up to five iterations of review by contributors, finalize content and layout, and deliver files to NSF for online publication. Desired completion date is February 2010.

5.1 CORE SUPPORT

Core Support includes program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects and cannot be attributed to a specific project.

Accomplishments To-Date for Year 2 (2009)

Continued support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

Remaining Activities for Year 2 (2009)

Continue Core Support of CA activities; staff time, however, will be allocated to direct projects as much as possible.

Planned Activities for Year 3 (2010)

Continue support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

Plans for SEARCH-ARCSS Integration

Background and Summary of Discussions To-Date

Over the past few years, the SEARCH and ARCSS communities have discussed the increasing need for improved integration and coordination between SEARCH and ARCSS and their respective planning processes, as there is considerable overlap in scientific focus and goals. There is now particular overlap between ARCSS synthesis efforts and the “Understanding Change” component of SEARCH, although there are also potential connections between ARCSS and SEARCH’s “Observing Change” and “Responding to Change” components.

After discussion at the 2008 SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) meeting, which included representatives from the ARCSS Committee, the SEARCH SSC and ARCSS Committee agreed to move forward with a joint planning process to align efforts for more efficient scientific planning and implementation and to explore scientific synergies. Discussions amongst the SEARCH SSC, the ARCSS Committee, and NSF have continued since then and culminated in a small face-to-face meeting at NSF in Arlington, Virginia on 15–16 September 2009. This meeting included NSF program directors and representatives of the SEARCH SSC and ARCSS Committee. The discussion ended with consensus recommendations for a series of activities over the next year to join the two efforts to accelerate our understanding of the arctic system and rapid environmental change.

There was broad agreement that we need to restructure the current planning processes to make them more nimble, able to respond to the scientific challenges of rapid arctic change, and incorporate multiple and concurrent approaches to addressing research needs. An approach is required that facilitates a broader array of responses to challenges, from individual proposals, to synthetic workshops, to comprehensive research programs.

The transition to a new model of integrated planning will be charted and guided by an ad hoc task force, comprised of members from the SEARCH, ARCSS, and other relevant communities. With the formation of the task force, the existing ARCSS Committee will cease to exist, and ARCSS-relevant science planning activities will be addressed in the short term by the ad hoc task force. The longer term structure and activities will be developed as the task force activities are completed, with guidance from the broader science community.

Recommendations: SEARCH-ARCSS Effort to Advance Understanding of the Arctic

1. Convene an ad hoc SEARCH-ARCSS “Understanding” Task Force – An ad hoc task force will be convened to lead community activities to establish a long-term vision and provide the scientific framework of a modern effort for understanding the arctic system. This group, with input and review from the broader community, will identify needs for accelerated community capacity-building and understanding of the rapidly changing arctic system.

- Task force membership will be drawn from the ARCSS Committee, the SEARCH Understanding Change Panel, and others as needed. It would be convened by the

Appendix A. Plans for SEARCH/ARCSS Integration and “Understanding Change” Task Force

SEARCH SSC, and chaired jointly by Josh Schimel, Chair of the ARCSS Committee, and John Walsh, Chair of the SEARCH Understanding Change Panel.

- The task force will have a term of one year.

2. Product: White Paper on a Vision of “Understanding Arctic System Change”

A community white paper report will be developed to: (1) Identify key unknowns and key science questions for understanding arctic system change, and (2) Identify the next steps in synthesis activities, methodologies, mechanisms, and approaches to address the identified key science questions.

- The white paper will be developed through a series of community activities, including two meetings and open community comment and review. The final white paper will be completed in December 2010.
- The white paper will include clear linkages to “Observing Change” and “Responding to Change” activities and priorities.
- The audience for the white paper will include the arctic science community, agencies, and stakeholders, perhaps framed as a “multi-layered” document to address different audiences. The SEARCH Science Steering Committee will draw upon the white paper to guide specific activities.

3. General Timeline:

Fall 2009: Convene SEARCH-ARCSS “Understanding” ad hoc task force, establish charge, specific timeline, and activities.

January 2010: Initial meeting of task force.

March 2010: Report on initial framework at the State of the Arctic Conference.

Summer 2010: Larger workshop to develop draft white paper.

Early Fall 2010: Draft white paper released and open community input review.

December 2010: Final white paper released.

These activities will result in improved integration between the current SEARCH and ARCSS efforts, advance SEARCH “Understanding Change” activities, and improve our understanding of the arctic system. The process is designed to allow ideas and vision to grow from the scientific community and inform viable research programs. The result will include identification of key scientific and structural needs, with a range of activities emerging to address those needs and a focus on nimble and decentralized structures.

SEARCH Science Steering Committee Meeting

5–6 November 2009
Washington Plaza Hotel
Franklin Room, Lobby Level
10 Thomas Circle, NW
Washington, DC

DRAFT: Summary Notes and Action Items

A SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Meeting was held 5–6 November 2009 in Washington, DC. Participants included SEARCH SSC members, IPMC members, and invited guests. The final agenda and PowerPoints are available through the meeting pages at: http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2009/ssc_nov/index.php (background documents available shortly).

Welcome, Introductions, and Overview of SEARCH Activities and Status

Peter Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair

[Will link to PPT and background document]

- The meeting started with a welcome and participant introductions
- Peter provided an overview of SEARCH, including its structure and objectives, the evolution of SEARCH, implementation status, international collaborations, challenges, and immediate SEARCH needs
- Summarized with three points:
 - SEARCH is still in transition to an operational program
 - The special nature of the program (long-term, cross-domain, pan-arctic, international, multi-agency, socioeconomic focus) presents new challenges
 - New models for running fully implemented SEARCH in an operational mode are required for science community, agencies and support structure
- The most important decisions for this SSC meeting are for decisions to move forward the Understanding and Responding components of SEARCH
- What SEARCH is doing – building an integrated, cross-disciplinary research program is inherently difficult; also need to build the depth of the talent pool for leadership in system-wide studies, bridging physical and natural and social sciences.
- Specifically need more encouragement and effort to bring in social scientists and human dimensions experts, and those with expertise in ‘responding to change’ elements.

Observing Change

Hajo Eicken, Observing Change Panel (OCP) Chair

[will link to PPT, ADI Project Plan, ADI Task Force Members, AON Awards, ADI and CADIS webpages]

- Hajo reviewed current Observing Change Panel activities, including: SEARCH Data Advisory Group, interagency coordination of observing programs, participation in

Appendix B. November SEARCH SSC Meeting Notes

the Sea Ice Outlook, planning for the AON PI meeting (30 November-2 December), AON Design and Implementation (ADI) activities, and assessment of AON implementation status and priorities by the UCP. Summarized ADI status, design considerations, and plan for the ADI task force activities and timeline

- Regarding OCP membership, since Hajo will move to the position of SSC chair, Taneil Uttal and Craig Lee will take over as OCP co-chairs (with approval by SSC).
- Interagency Coordination of Observing: Issues for consideration for SSC include how to get a handle on the interagency coordination aspect.
 - Hajo – within the agencies, need people who have time and resources to develop integration /coordination. Basically people on detail to bring the parts together. Also could have more agency involvement in AON PI or ADI meetings
 - Wanda Ferrell (DOE) – discussion on how to better engage ARM/DOE. Should talk about this more, but for now can include ARM on CADIS site, and Hajo and Wanda to talk more – perhaps more SEARCH feedback into ARM data user meetings.
- Discussion of what defines success for AON. Hajo discussed two two different kinds of success. 1. Project level - Each project has own metrics of success, projects were asked to give 3-pagers to summarize projects' recent successes, 2. Putting things together to get more than the sum of its parts - not a lot of this kind of activity. For example, how are the observing activities actually linking up in the field? Document from the UCP reported that there is still duplication, etc., and that people are not thinking about more cross-project linkages
- Another definition of success might be the extent to which information and knowledge is used by people and entities that are responding to change
- Also discussion of whether SSC could be more of a coordinating, hands-on entity, rather than focusing on higher-level strategic planning. For example, defining products that the SSC would assist in developing (model products, etc.), or convening working groups on specific science questions. (e.g., how far in the future can we predict?, etc.)
- Discussion came back to activities of ADI – SSC agreed that ADI activities are useful, but suggested that there be more interaction/incorporation of responding to change.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Link to DOE ARM data through CADIS site (Hajo to relay)
- Consider other agencies to attend AON PI meeting to discuss interagency coordination (Hajo)
- Hajo and Wanda discuss further Observing linkages to ARM (Hajo)
- SSC agreed that ADI is a good direction, with more interaction with Responding to Change. Hajo to bring back to the ADI group (Hajo)

Understanding Change

(Peter Schlosser)

[Will link to background documents: SEARCH-ARCSS Understanding Integration, Understanding Change Panel document on AON, agency Understanding group]

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- Over the past several months, Peter, Hajo, ARCUS, Josh Schimel (Chair of ARCSS Committee) have been working on a proposed plan to integrate ARCSS and SEARCH, as there is considerable overlap in scientific focus and goals
- This plan essentially consists of convening an ad hoc task force, chaired by Josh Schimel and John Walsh (Chair of the SEARCH UCP) to lead community activities to establish a long-term vision and provide the scientific framework of a modern effort for understanding the arctic system. A community white paper report will be developed to: (1) Identify key unknowns and key science questions for understanding arctic system change, and (2) Identify the next steps in synthesis activities, methodologies, mechanisms, and approaches to address the identified key science questions. White paper would be finalized December 2010.
- The ARCSS Committee met to discuss the proposed plan before this SEARCH SSC meeting, and agreed that it should be moved forward.
- The SSC discussed the plan and agreed it should be moved forward.
- NSF reported that there are no immediate plans for an Understanding Change AO, and NSF will wait to decide future plans based on what emerges from this task force process.

ACTION ITEMS:

- ARCUS to move forward the task force plan, beginning with discussions with Josh Schimel and John Walsh, co-chairs of the task force (ARCUS)
- Will report back to SSC when co-chairs at the point of recommendations for task force members – goal for early December (ARCUS, Co-chairs)

Responding to Change

Peter Schlosser and Maribeth Murray

- Last SSC meeting, SSC had suggested a workshop should be planned to move forward Responding to Change component; this workshop was not planned within the SEARCH context, as ISAC was moving forward on similar plans for a Responding to change white paper and workshop.
- Maribeth Murray reported that ISAC held an SSG meeting at the end of September – plans are underway to draft a white paper for discussion purposes on Responding to Change. There will be a meeting at AGU on this, and ISAC hopes to release the paper at the State of the Arctic. A Responding to Change workshop, led by ISAC, will be planned for summer/fall 2010.
- It was noted by several members that one big challenge facing Responding to Change planning and implementation is lack of capacity (i.e., experts in the field), and this is a pan-arctic problem, not just U.S. or SEARCH. ISAC efforts are strongly directed towards bringing in people doing human dimensions work in other parts of the world, e.g., IHDP. Expanding capacity requires us to go to global community. Other regions are further ahead in doing applied and integrated work.
- Also a challenge is *defining* Responding to Change – what we mean specifically as far as issues of adaptation and mitigation and human dimensions in the SEARCH context.
- Short discussion on the Responding to Change panel, which is not currently active, as the former chair (Jack Kruse) has stepped down. It was agreed that reconstitution

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of the panel would be put on hold until the ISAC Responding to Change white paper was complete, so that members could be chosen to fit the intellectual directions of the Responding planning activities

- SSC agreed to work with ISAC on developing an intellectual framework for Responding to Change – with initial activities being contributions to the white paper and workshop planning.

ACTION ITEMS:

- SEARCH to participate in ISAC white paper development and workshop planning – Identify a few SEARCH people to work with Maribeth on the process to develop an intellectual framework and plan for Responding (Peter, Hajo, ARCUS)
- Create a one-page description of activities; Neil Swanberg (NSF) can use that to engage the IPMC, including request for travel support for US participants to the Responding to Change workshop in 2010 (Maribeth)

SEARCH Data Advisory Group

Steve Oberbauer, Data Group Chair (via phone)

[will reference PPT]

- The SEARCH Data Advisory Group was reconstituted since the last SSC meeting (as an action item from the last SEARCH SSC meeting) to focus on data management/coordination with regard to AON.
- The Data Advisory Group expanded its membership to include a cyberinfrastructure expert and a data user (as per suggestions from last SSC meeting). The Data Group membership includes: Carin Ashjian, Dave McGuire, Don Perovich, R.M. Holmes, Steve Oberbauer, and new members: Judy Cushing (Evergreen State – cyberinfrastructure), Julio Ibarra (Florida International University - cyberinfrastructure), and John Kimball (University of Montana - data user).
- The Data Group currently has a charge for the following activities:
 1. Provide use cases for CADIS
 2. Explore CADIS site
 3. Provide feedback on a series of issues/capabilities for CADIS
- The goal of the data group is to have feedback on the above ready to present at the AON PI meeting, 30 November–2 December.
- These data group activities will continue after the AON PI meeting
- [Steve O. phone went out at this point]
- Hajo – the data group is focused on observing/AON now because that is what is currently funded for actual projects
- The CADIS site is undergoing a change to its interface, so the data group will do thorough exploration and feedback once the new interface is launched.
- Discussion on improving the way data management serves people outside the scientific community, as well as serving the Understanding and Responding aspects of SEARCH science.
- Several members discussed specific directions that CADIS could consider, including incorporating expert systems research (suggestion from Caspar Amman) and

Appendix B. November SEARCH SSC Meeting Notes

getting input from experts on decision-support tools (suggestion from Maribeth and Larry Hamilton).

ACTION ITEMS:

- Send information to the data group on expert systems (Caspar Amman)
- Send information/recommendations to the group regarding expertise on decision-support tools (Maribeth or Larry)
- Work with the Observing and Understanding panels (and ISAC for Responding to Change) to get input on issues of AON data needs, e.g., what level of AON data should be made available, what kinds of products, level of pre-processing; to including consideration of users outside of the scientific community (Steve)
- Post updated information on the data group on the SEARCH website (ARCUS)

State of the Arctic Conference (SoA)

Peter Schlosser

[See website at: <http://soa.arcus.org/>, also see internal program]

- SSC members discussed overall structure, program, and parallel session topics. Plenary speakers have been invited and many accepted. Parallel theme topics are being finalized by the Executive Committee, after input from the Organizing Committee (and from this SSC meeting).
- Peter – Desired outcome of the conference is to help us think through what kind of research is needed compared to what is being done? What kind of research programs are needed? How do we need to refine, augment, and shape existing programs in the future to meet these needs? For example, how to design an arctic observing system, or how can we contribute to solutions in the Arctic.
- SSC members discussed incorporation of young investigators – could be done in panel, as well as travel support. The SOA OC has already convened a small committee to discuss plans for student/young investigator involvement.
- Need funds to support young investigators – have some through IASC. Would be good way for other IPMC agencies to support the conference. Also could design an award that focuses on the best “SEARCH” poster abstract, e.g. crosses disciplinary boundaries, incorporates human dimensions, etc.
- Discussed products – it is expected that a set of papers in journals, perhaps a special issue of journal will be produced. Also a compilation of all the abstracts. Some discussion of a book, but several members expressed concern about the time and work that will be required for a book, also that online venues are more utilized now. Members agreed that products should provide a larger synthetic view. Also consider a way to publish posters.
- Discussed media/press involvement. ARCUS has asked for RFPs from Miami-local PR agencies to contract for this purpose. Media advisories should be done for selected sessions. AAAS has a program that we could model from.
- Discussed ways to engage IPMC and other agencies – add language to website that encourages agency involvement; Neil offered to help through the IPMC.

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ACTION ITEMS:

- Send the latest internal program to the SSC (ARCUS)
- Parallel sessions/abstract call should be worded so that each session can incorporate human dimensions (ARCUS – complete)
- Go forward with media plan, including media advisories and looking into AAAS program for ideas (ARCUS – Teleconference with NSF media liaison scheduled for 16 Nov).
- Further discussion needed on products, including a method to publish posters (SoA Organizing Committee)
- Further discuss student poster award program, including an award for best “SEARCH” abstract (SoA Organizing Committee)
- Engage agencies through: drafting language on website that encourages agency participation, letter/information to IPMC (through Neil) (ARCUS work with Neil)
- Engage global HD community into SoA (ARCUS work with Maribeth)
- ARCUS outreach into Alaska-based agency personnel (ARCUS)
- Plan to print/send panels available from the Smithsonian’s Friend Acting Strangely exhibit (ARCUS work with Bill Fitzhugh)

SEARCH Sea Ice Outlook (SIO)

James Overland (Chair of SIO core group) (by phone) and Hajo Eicken (for Regional Outlook)

[will link to PPT and website at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/index.php>]

- The 2009 Sea Ice Outlook was as a success. Over 15 groups participated
- Take home points for this year: while 2009 was 3rd lowest summer extent, fall freeze up was very late. Multi-year sea ice was very low. The Arctic is still behaving with extremes.
- Hajo – One of recommendations from last year was to include a regional outlook – so we did that this year. Eight (8) groups provided a regional outlook, and 5 out of the 8 were “right on” with outlooks. An interesting pattern with the outlooks this year was that for the pan-arctic scale, coupled ensemble predictions were best; at the regional scale, the coupled ensemble predictions did the worst. In order to make the regional outlooks more useful in the future, will have more guidance and rigor – will be involving a post-doc working with Canadian Ice Center for next year’s regional outlooks.
- Web presence for the Sea Ice Outlook has been a success. [ARCUS web stats: the SIO website (about 350 pages of content) has been viewed 45,276 times since Jan 1 of this year, with 34,916 of those as “unique” pageviews (i.e., taking out instances of a visitor going back to a page over again on one visit). Visitors were from all over the world - 60.6% from Americas, 32.9% from Europe, and some from Oceania (3.5%), Asia (2.5%), and Africa (<1%)].
- IPY office considers SIO one of the main key activities that have happened in IPY. AWI, Stockholm group also views SIO as one of their major activities
- Plan to continue the SIO in 2010

Appendix B. November SEARCH SSC Meeting Notes

- Priority for winter 2010: Work with other groups to define priority arctic observations that would help support the outlook goals, e.g., observations on ocean heat content, visual reconnaissance of ice types; develop recommendations from Outlook on priority AON observations/needs. The Outlook approach can be used to move forward issues such as uncoordinated ocean observations – by using the Outlook (the gaps in observations for models) as a way to prioritize and highlight observation needs.
- Will have Sea Ice Outlook meeting at AGU in the ARCUS community meeting room.
- SSC members discussed ideas and recommendations for next year's Outlook, including expanding the Outlook to the cold season, an outlook for the sea ice maximum, and integration with real-time observations (e.g. from cruises)
- Also need to discuss further how for 2011, how to ensure this is a sustained activity in SEARCH, perhaps through a standing SEARCH working group or other means.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Discuss SSC suggestions, as well as community suggestions, as move forward with planning for the 2010 Outlook.
- Further discuss stable support structure for the Outlook, including resources for lead contributors' time (e.g., 2 weeks-1 month of salary support).

Implementing SEARCH through Multi-Agency Cooperation

Neil Swanberg, National Science Foundation; Chair, SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC)

[Will request a short formal written statement (and PPT, if available) from each agency to post on website.]

Overview of Agency Activities:

- *National Science Foundation (NSF)* - Neil Swanberg
 - Besides funding science, a major NSF SEARCH effort is the OPERA AO (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2009/nsf09599/nsf09599.htm>, deadline of 11 December 2009), which is focused on infrastructural support for SEARCH, including science infrastructure. \$5m a year, about ½ to data.
 - AON – PPT presentation from Martin Jeffries.
- *National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)* - John Calder
 - Many contributions to SEARCH through climate and atmospheric observing activities
- *Department of Energy (DOE)* - Wanda Ferrell
 - DOE contributes to the SEARCH program through climate modeling, ARM data, Barrow infrastructure/equipment, etc.
 - With ARM, DOE would like to engage SEARCH on the user advisory group
- *Smithsonian Institution* - Bill Fitzhugh
 - Smithsonian does not fund research, but focuses on collaboration and outreach. Several Smithsonian activities, including arctic exhibits to the Anchorage museum, and the “Arctic: A Friend Acting Strangely” exhibit.

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- Discussion on including a traveling portion of the “Friend Acting Strangely” as exhibit at the State of the Arctic.
- *National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)* - Thomas Wagner
 - [Will link to PPT]
 - NASA’s goal in the polar regions is to understand how they are changing, especially how changes in ocean circulation are occurring and how it relates to sea ice cover and land based ice.
 - Several SEARCH relevant projects and investments include climate experiments, sensors, and quantifying changes in sea and ice sheets. Also interested in permafrost and arctic rivers.
- U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) - No representative attended.
- Department of the Interior (DOI) - No representative attended.
- Department of Defense (DOD) - No representative attended.

IPMC as Interagency Coordination Body

- SSC members noted that the IPMC is now more important than ever, as SEARCH is moving from planning phase to implementation and coordination. This is especially important for launching Responding to Change activities.
- There is a need for outreach into the agencies about SEARCH, specifically about State of the Arctic.
- Discussion of challenges in multi-agency cooperation, including frustration by agency personnel in having too many meetings to attend, and the time needed for agency coordination.
- Need more IPMC interaction on a regular basis, also on an ad hoc basis for various topics, and discussions with SSC.
- Actual funds are needed for agency coordination.
- For State of the Arctic, can work with Neil to get into agencies, add a page or paragraph on website that will bring in agencies, etc. Specifically more topical issues; have agencies/IPMC reps translate parallel themes into bullets friendly to their agency.

Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC)

- See website at: <http://www.nsf.gov/od/opp/arctic/iarpc/start.jsp>
- There is an IARPC principals meeting in February. SSC discussed this as a good opportunity to present SEARCH interagency needs. Specifically SoA, as well as discussing a better process for interagency coordination.

SAON (John Calder)

- See website at: <http://saon.arcticportal.org/>
- SAON is an international process to find a way to continue and enhance observing activities. Focus on three items in the coming year – 1. Improve data management, 2. Linking modern science and traditional knowledge, 3. Bring together officials of agencies who support or conduct observing (will have meeting at State of the Arctic). SAON is focused on cooperation, facilitation, and synergy, as well as thinking about the institutional framework.
- There is some confusion in the community about the purpose of SAON – recommend that SAON communicate/update the community to clarify activities and goals.

ACTION ITEMS:

- DOE engage SEARCH on ARM advisory group/activities (Hajo follow-up)
- SSC members recommended that SAON group clarify to the community the recent activities and goals of SAON (John Calder)
- Discuss possible need/recommendations from SSC for IPMC meeting/telecon as follow-up to SSC for SoA (Peter, Hajo)
- Ask NOAA to link Arctic Report Card/NOAA arctic webpages clearly with SEARCH (ARCUS)
- Work with Neil to get SEARCH on the next IARPC principals meeting, including State of the Arctic, and Responding to Change needs (Peter, Hajo)
- See State of the Arctic section, above, for agency-focused action items related to the conference.

Freshwater Integration study (FWI)

Charles Vörösmarty

[Will link to PPT]

- See website at: <http://arcticchamp.sr.unh.edu/index.shtml>
- Vörösmarty gave an informational presentation on results, activities, and plans in the FWI “sunset phase”
- Next steps in FWI include:
 - Produce strategic document on gaps/opportunities for new research and shorter “communique” (e.g. in AGU-Eos)
 - Organizing team to meet in Victoria (BC), 10th-11th January to begin formal drafting process
 - Publication target: mid-2010

ACTION ITEMS:

None.

Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) / Bering Sea Integrated Ecosystem Research Program (BSIERP)

William Wiseman, NSF

- See website at: <http://bsierp.nprb.org/>
- The BEST/BSIERP program has about 100 investigators ; 2 years of field work has been completed and modeling activities are progressing.
- With regard to linkages between SEARCH and BEST – Bering Sea is arctic according to Congress... lots of linkages to arctic with science, environmental changes, etc. Good model of agency cooperation, really good collaboration between the PIs – whether NSF or NPRB funded

ACTION ITEMS:

- SEARCH talk to BEST/BSIERP to discuss possible mutual interest in stronger collaboration and synergies with SEARCH (Peter and Hajo)
- Approach BEST/BSIERP for participation at State of the Arctic (ARCUS)

Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES)

Jean-Claude Gascard

[will link to PPT]

- See website at: <http://www.damocles-eu.org/>
- Informational presentation focused on the DAMOCLES symposium, “The Arctic Climate System, its Present Status, Future Evolution and Potential Impacts,” organized by the Damocles Steering Committee in Brussels, on November 10-12, 2009. Craig Lee and Peter will be representing SEARCH.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Further discussion with DAMOCLES on future collaborations, extension of MOU, etc (Peter)

ArcticNet Activities and Plans

Martin Fortier (Via phone)

[will link to PPT]

- See website at: <http://www.arcticnet.ulaval.ca/>
- Presented ArcticNet – objectives, activities, partnerships (specifically with industry)
- Discussed opportunities for collaboration between ArcticNet and SEARCH. Move forward on MOU (joint projects, student exchange, etc.) – target to have draft MOU at SoA. Also Martin will send suggestions for ArcticNet person to go to ADI meeting (Martin cannot attend).

ACTION ITEMS:

- Convene a few SEARCH representatives from various disciplines and ArcticNet together to talk about concrete areas for collaboration (Peter, Hajo, ARCUS)
- Move forward on an MOU with Arctic (joint projects, student exchange, etc) – target to have draft MOU at State of the Arctic (ARCUS)
- Martin will send suggestions for an ArcticNet person to go to ADI meeting (Martin)

International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC)

Maribeth Murray

[will link to PPT and ISAC Science Plan executive summary]

- See website at: <http://www.arcticchange.org/>
- Presentation on ISAC program history, and recent and planned activities
- Upcoming activities include:
 - ISAC Open Science Discussion, AGU Annual Fall Meeting, 2009
 - State of the Arctic Meeting, 2010. Miami. Joint sponsorship with DAMOCLES and SEARCH and others. 4th Day – International Cooperation in Arctic Science. White paper on Responding to Change to carry ISAC into the future
 - Responding to Change Workshop (ca. 50 people), Summer/Fall 2010.

Appendix B. November SEARCH SSC Meeting Notes

ISAC issues were discussed in the context of Responding to Change – see that section, above, for all action items

Discussion of SEARCH and “Organization of Projects on Environmental Research in the Arctic” (OPERA) NSF Announcement of Opportunity (AO)

- See AO at: <http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2009/nsf09599/nsf09599.htm>
- Neil Swanberg introduced the OPERA AO release by NSF, deadline for proposals is 11 December 2009. NSF laid down a challenge to IPMC in 2007 to help support SEARCH activities, but not enough support coming to SEARCH infrastructure, especially at the panel level (panel activities are currently all volunteer). Need dedicated scientific support and more activities. The AO was written to avoid being prescriptive.
- Not solely for SEARCH, but intended to serve SEARCH
- \$15M over 3 years, with large portion for data
- Peter – posed question on whether the role of the SSC will substantially be changed, or rather will the OPERA projects be in support of the scientific directions laid out by the SSC
- Neil – NSF tried to wordcraft that in the AO – they still see SSC as planning and thinking center for SEARCH. They expect OPERA candidates to responsive to the SEARCH planning process. SEARCH will also have to be responsive to OPERA-funded groups.
- Hajo – this will give us a new way of working, would like to see a lot of good ideas being tested and one or several emerge as most viable, then working with whatever group is funded. Mix of anxiety and enthusiasm. Anxiety related to some of the wording in the AO. What’s going to be important is to maintain the SSC and panels – let their ideas emerge to work with whatever is funded with OPERA.
- Hajo - Question for NSF is if the SSC will have input into the review process.
- Neil – it will depend on what comes in.
- Peter – hope that proposals will help move things forward that SEARCH is already initiated (like ADI, Understanding Task Force, etc).
- Neil – intent is to *add* to current ‘volunteer’ support.
- Neil – may be office or some offices with post-docs, etc., to carry out some of the activities – synthesis, etc, looking for imaginative ideas.
- Peter – when transitioning into a new system under OPERA, will have transparency on what is underway with SEARCH and what is needed.
- Neil – sometime next summer, OPERA funded people will come to SEARCH and will need to work together. So where will SEARCH be a year from now, a few years from now, what is the vision? Challenge to SSC to think about long-term vision.
- Peter – Do we have to re-write our Science Plan? Or is the Science plan that ISAC is finalizing – is that the vision that will hold for the next 5 years? We aren’t lacking the grand vision
- Neil – SEARCH should be changing – is it going to be doing something with actual funded projects, etc? Work with other programs, etc?

Appendix B. November SEARCH SSC Meeting Notes

- Hajo – the challenge is, to be blunt about it, the way people have thought about SEARCH has evolved – there is a vision, but what is going to happen about it? Questions like joint research with industry remain.
- Peter – past frustration as SEARCH SSC chair – getting people to understand that responding to change is most important of three components
- Steve Vavrus – that can be one of the starting points – gives us an idea on where to go with this and a connection with OPERA.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Continue to post as much information as possible on SEARCH activities to the website, to help in transition to OPERA-funded support (ARCUS).

SSC and Panel Membership

- Held off rotation last year to give Hajo, as incoming chair, room to shape the membership
- Discussion of how we need to develop SSC over the next months, and the capacity in which the SSC should work – e.g., whether to move to a more hands-on approach, like synthesis, project coordination, etc.
- SSC needs to be more explicit about what they want in the social sciences and human dimensions. Young scientists from the interdisciplinary community would be useful for the social science aspect. One issue is avoiding any detrimental effects to young career scientist careers – need to go to administrative levels to help change this culture. Also could consider proposals, trainingships that would be beneficial to SEARCH.
- Hajo proposes Peter act as out-going chair for one year. Peter and Hajo will discuss this further.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Hajo will look at SSC member rotation schedules, etc, then further dialog. Peter to send rotation schedule. (Peter, Hajo)
- Peter to decide if he accepts position as outgoing chair for one year (Peter, Hajo)
- Move forward on appointing Craig Lee and Taneil Uttal as chairs of the OCP (Hajo, ARCUS)
- Hold on any appointments to the Understanding Panel, until task force activities are complete or produce guidance for that panel
- Hold on any appointments/reconstitution of the Responding panel, until ISAC activities (white paper, workshop) can help define the Responding component

Other Business

- SSC members expressed gratitude to Peter for his work and dedication to SEARCH
- Determine timeframe/venue for next SSC meeting (eMeeting and/or in person) (Hajo, ARCUS)

Collaborative Research: Task force for design, optimization, and implementation of the Arctic Observing Network – Phase I

Start date: September 1, 2009, duration: 12 months

PI: Hajo Eicken, co-I: John Walsh (at UAF, lead institution)

PI: Peter Schlosser (Columbia University, collaborating institution)

Project Summary

Recent and ongoing Arctic environmental and socio-economic change has highlighted the need for a comprehensive observing system that tracks such change to foster understanding of the driving processes and the interaction between system components, thereby allowing society to anticipate and plan for future changes still to come. Building an effective, scientifically robust Arctic Observing Network (AON) requires planning, coordination and analysis of data and model output over a range of disciplines, as well as temporal and spatial scales. The International Polar Year (IPY) has facilitated a substantial enhancement of observation campaigns and deployment of sensor networks, ushering in a phase of more widespread observing efforts carried out by many countries. With US agencies and others maintaining complementary observation efforts in the Arctic, there is now an urgent need for coordination, consolidation and optimization of the existing observing system elements, as well as for development of a broader strategy that includes more detailed design studies to enhance and sustain the observing system.

This project implements Phase I of a 12-month process to provide guidance to the National Science Foundation, the scientific community and others engaged in Arctic environmental observations on how to best achieve a well-designed, effective and robust Arctic observing system. An AON Design and Implementation (ADI) Task Force, composed of researchers with observing-system expertise both within and outside of the Arctic, will work with other key experts to meet these objectives. Activities include a combination of virtual and in-person meetings, two workshops and a small array of proof-of-concept or exploratory studies overseen by the Task Force, culminating in a summary report with recommendations for the next steps in optimizing, coordinating, and enhancing the existing components of an international Arctic environmental observing system with emphasis on the AON. During Phase I of the project (this proposal), support is requested to facilitate activities up to and including the completion of the first workshop and a follow-up meeting.

Intellectual merit. The ADI activities will develop an overarching concept that will guide the next, necessary step in design and implementation of the U.S. AON as part of a coordinated, international, multi-disciplinary, long-term Arctic Observing System. The Task Force will explore and evaluate different approaches and methodologies of potential use in system design. Challenges that will be addressed include the broad, interdisciplinary scope of the AON, the goal to meet scientific, as well as stakeholder needs, and the requirement to be adaptive during a period of rapid change.

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Broader impacts. The ADI process will help ensure that the AON efforts will yield results that will advance our scientific understanding of the Arctic system and its variability and change, and at the same time aid individuals, communities and the nation in adapting and responding to rapid environmental change in the Arctic. Involvement of experts from outside the Arctic research community will broaden impacts by strengthening the ties between Arctic and lower-latitude observation programs. A report and recommendations will be circulated widely to further stimulate the discourse about the refinement of the Arctic Observing System towards optimal design and implementation.

1. Introduction and Background

The need for an Arctic Observing Network (AON) that tracks and fosters understanding of the complex of rapid Arctic environmental change presently underway, thereby improving projections of, and adaptation to, anticipated future change has been broadly recognized (SEARCH, 2003, 2005; NRC, 2006; IARPC, 2007). In response to this critical need, the scientific community has identified a broad set of key scientific questions in the context of the Study of Environmental Arctic Change's Science Plan (2001) and Implementation Workshop Report (SEARCH, 2005). Building an effective, scientifically robust AON requires planning, coordination and analysis of data and model output over a range of disciplines and scales. The International Polar Year (IPY) has fostered a substantial push for intense observation campaigns and deployment of sensor networks, ushering in a phase of more coordinated observing efforts. Of these, three programs are of particular relevance: the SEARCH AON, the European DAMOCLES program (Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies, winding down but spawning sustained observing efforts) and the Canadian ArcticNet Program. With US agencies and others maintaining complementary observation efforts in the Arctic, there is now an urgent need for coordination, consolidation and optimization of the existing observing system elements, as well as for development of a broader strategy that includes more detailed design studies to enhance and sustain the observing system. There is also an unprecedented opportunity to use the wealth of available observations from the Arctic to exploit their synergies and assess their contributions to a holistic depiction of the state of the Arctic.

This proposal seeks to take the first step in implementing a 12-month process to explore and define different options and provide guidance to the National Science Foundation (NSF), the scientific community and others engaged in Arctic environmental observations on how to best achieve a well-designed, effective and robust U.S. Arctic observing efforts in the context of ongoing efforts to optimize and implement an international Arctic observing system. A Task Force of experts in the Arctic and broader scientific community knowledgeable in observing system design and related fields will work with other key experts to achieve these goals. Activities will include a combination of virtual and in-person meetings, two workshops and a small array of proof-of-concept or exploratory studies overseen by the Task Force, culminating in a report and recommendations to NSF.

Arctic Observing System Design Considerations

The planned activities will need to consider the following issues that define the nascent US AON. These traits distinguish the AON to some extent from previous efforts in other arenas, such as the Tropical Atmosphere Ocean/Triangle Trans-Ocean Buoy Network (TAO/TRITON, McPhaden et al., 2009), or the Long-Term Ecological Research network (Hobbie et al., 2003), among others. This is both an opportunity for truly transformative research but also poses a significant challenge, that will likely guide the Task Force approach. From the perspective of SEARCH and its observing component,

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the US AON, a number of issues arise that need to be considered by individual researchers, the community involved in the implementation of the observing system, and funding agencies who support the system.

- (i) *Guidance by science questions*: The observing system has to be guided by the science questions that underpin the Arctic environmental change programs (SEARCH for the US and the International Study of Arctic Change; ISAC, as the emerging international umbrella). These science questions have matured during the past years and are captured in the several science plans, most recently in the ISAC science plan (ISAC, 2009).
- (ii) *Comprehensive nature of observing effort*: The broad range of questions and disciplines that are part of the observing system presents a challenge to traditional approaches in designing and maintaining an appropriately balanced observing system (e.g., remote sensing vs. ground-based, (synoptic) surveys vs. point-based measurements, broad regions of interest).
- (iii) *Coordination of measurement activities*: Individual projects derive guidance on specifics of measurement activities from broader program plans and project goals, but intercomparability and thematic compatibility of data sets require additional efforts in determining sampling rates, spatial resolution of measurements, site selection, and variables to be measured. International coordination, for example through initiatives such as ISAC, can help maximize synergy, e.g., through joint workshops or meetings on a regular schedule.
- (iv) *Need for observing system to be highly adaptive*: The rate of change in the Arctic, in particular in relation to standard funding cycles or the response times of international research organizations and programs, requires new approaches in the design and optimization of an observing system. The complexity of the problem, the fast pace of change and the importance of observing the anthroposphere in the context of SEARCH require that the observing system be highly adaptive, allowing for the system to evolve on the timescales required to track rapid change and plan for effective response. Abrupt changes that have to be expected in the transition of the Arctic into a new state pose challenges for the observing system, specifically concerning its capacity for high sampling rates.
- (v) *Dual purpose of AON*: SEARCH explicitly identified the need for an Arctic observing system to serve the scientific community as well as serving information needs of key stakeholder groups. This duality of purpose requires novel approaches with respect to the design of an observing network, but will likely result in transformative research on the coupling between human activities and environmental change.
- (vi) *Inter-disciplinary nature of an observing system*: The interdisciplinary nature of many of the pressing SEARCH science questions and societal needs require a multi-disciplinary observing network with a degree of disciplinary intertwining and topical breadth that is pioneering at this scale. At present, funded AON projects (from CADIS web site, retrieved 24 April 2009) comprise the following topical areas: atmosphere (7), ocean and sea ice (18), hydrology and cryosphere (6), terrestrial ecosystems (3), human dimensions (1), data management and coordination (2). The current portfolio may change as the program evolves, and may require guidance to ensure the disciplinary balance needed to meet the

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overarching scientific goals of the program. At the same time, the concentration of atmosphere-ocean-sea ice projects reflects critical information needs and scientific opportunities.

Ideally, one would like to base the design and implementation of a complex observing system on a comprehensive theoretical framework with the following attributes:

- (a) Capability to optimize distribution and mix of sensors for the set of variables that are identified by interpretation of existing data through synthesis, modeling and scale analyses.
- (b) Exploration of tradeoffs between deployment of sensors for different variables and data streams that primarily satisfy scientific needs vs. those that satisfy primarily stakeholder information.
- (c) Examination of irreversible loss of information on the Arctic system dynamics through termination or re-location of time series measurements.
- (d) Determination of accuracy at which variables have to be measured to yield the information needed for answering the science questions underpinning the observing system.

Unfortunately, such theoretical frameworks are currently not available and will not be available for the foreseeable future because they depend on the capability to describe the dynamics of the integrated Arctic system in a 4-dimensional fashion. De facto, a fully coupled, multi-domain Arctic system model is needed as the starting point for such a theoretical approach to an observing system design. While steps toward the development of such a model are underway, there will continue to be a need for a more pragmatic and empirically based approach to ensure expedience in maximizing the return from investments into system-scale, integrated, long-term observing systems.

Empirical Approach to Arctic Observing System Design

The implementation of a sustained, pan-Arctic observing system can be considered as a hierarchy of sub-problems (Fig. 1). However, since implementation has progressed and continues to evolve at all levels of this hierarchy, questions of observing system design cannot be addressed in isolation (bottom-up or top-down) but need to be considered in the context of existing efforts. This process is naturally challenging but it allows continuation of the implementation of an increasingly complex and optimized observing system. Significant benefits can be derived from the synergistic implementation of different studies, initiatives and programs already underway. One promising strategy to draw on such benefits is to anchor the design and planning of the observing system in the context of the hierarchy shown in Fig. 1. The science questions that drive the observing system are well established and already guide the implementation of individual projects as well as that of the integrated system. The linkages between individual projects in the context of overarching trans-disciplinary programs such as SEARCH or ISAC is emerging but presently not fully developed. Similarly, there are emerging benefits from international coordination and implementation although this process is still in an exploratory stage (e.g., SEARCH for DAMOCLES).

It should be emphasized that although lacking a theoretically based approach, observing system design is already actively underway on a scientifically informed basis.

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For example, individual projects use information on the dynamics of the system including spatial and temporal scales of movement of air, water and ice for system design (Rigor et al., 2002; Lindsay and Zhang, 2006; Lee et al., 2009). They also make use of existing data sets by artificially reducing the data density in sections until some of the prominent features can no longer be resolved. Terrestrial observations utilize information on typical vegetation migration rates from modern or paleo-observations to design an observing program that would capture future northward migration of specific species (Jia et al., 2003). Modeling studies are increasingly analyzed for information on critical time scales, particle tracking to simulate Lagrangian experiments, or Eulerian type time series sampling to infer expected frequencies and amplitudes of perturbations at fixed points (Maslowski et al., 2000). These empirical designs are becoming more sophisticated as the data sets increase and the models are able to more realistically simulate processes in nature. Stakeholder information needs that inform an observing system can be assessed and prioritized through an analysis of services provided by the system and the institutions that govern use of these services (Eicken et al., 2009).

Figure 1: Schematic of a hierarchy of approaches and activities governing design and implementation of an Arctic observing system. Note that the science questions in the left column have been separated into those primarily driven by fundamental research questions (left) and those that include specific information needs by different stakeholders (right, marked with

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asterisk). While this division is artificial (ultimately, all science questions meet societal information needs) it is helpful in organizing and prioritizing different research efforts.

Most of the methods described above are applied to design observing activities on the scale that can be handled by single PI's or by PI groups. The design of system-scale, single-domain observing systems is still lagging behind the design of individual, geographically limited components, in terms of sophistication and optimization. Even more work has to be done to optimize observing system components that cross domains although these are exactly the type of observing systems that are needed for modern, theme-driven, system-based studies. Tackling these tasks has to be given immediate attention and high priority for effective observing system design and implementation and will be a key concern to the AON Design and Implementation (ADI) Task Force.

A significant challenge remains in particular for those components of an observing system that focus on the upper trophic levels of ecosystems and human activities. Time-space grids may work well for relatively static landscapes (such as in agricultural applications), but do not fit the dynamic and patchy distribution of animals and people in the Arctic. The observing system must be able to track specific populations that are present in discrete locations over space and time and be able to adapt observation efforts to best match the dynamics of these communities.

2. Objectives and Scope of ADI Task Force Activities and Related Efforts

The following objectives can guide the ADI Task Force activities and supporting efforts by the SEARCH panels and Science Steering Committee (SSC) and other relevant steering groups towards improvement of observing system design:

- (a) evaluate the current implementation status of the Arctic Observing System vis-à-vis the key science questions identified by the Arctic research community;
- (b) improve design and adaptation of observing system components through observing system simulation experiments and similar approaches;
- (c) synthesize information arriving from the existing observing system components and quantitative design studies to guide its design and refinement;
- (d) coordinate between individual national and international efforts. Here, ISAC can help with international aspects of coordination.

A process that would advance these goals and the urgent need for guidance on AON design and implementation identified above would include the following tasks:

(1) Assessment of the present state and near-term implementation plans of the AON and related efforts

SEARCH mainly through members of its SSC, and the Observing Change and Understanding Change Panels (OCP, UCP), with a few key contributors from the Arctic System Science Program (ARCSS) and the broader Arctic community have begun to prepare an assessment of the AON in its current form (under leadership of co-I John Walsh, UCP Chair). This review will examine how well the existing system addresses the major Arctic Change science questions, identify newly emergent, high-priority science questions or drivers that should augment those in the SEARCH plan, as well as identify critical gaps or needs and make recommendations for the next steps in the integration of

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observing system efforts. A starting point for this activity is the Report from the 2008 Arctic Observations Integration Workshop (<http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/aow/report.php>) which contains both a mix of very specific and very broad recommendations. Some of these need to be revisited, but significant guidance can be derived from the Workshop's 10 short-term recommendations. This activity would lead to a brief report that the ADI Task Force can draw on to allow for more effective and rapid progress.

(2) Identifying and assessing effective, promising approaches and tools for observing system design and optimization

This objective would be at the core of the ADI Task Force's charge. Given the lack of a comprehensive theoretical framework for observing system design and optimization applicable to the AON, the Task Force likely will have to consider a broad array of methods that provide information on the performance and options for future enhancement of the observing system. These methods include observing system simulation experiments (OSSE), evaluation of the information coming from the data assimilation community (e.g., reanalysis and forecasting projects, Bromwich et al., 2008) or tools such as manipulation of data sets to examine the data density required to capture the processes that determine the characteristic features of the observed system components. This process needs coordination, an interface with the AON data management system (such as the Cooperative Arctic Data and Information System, CADIS) and the involvement of the modeling community.

To initiate this process, it is proposed to convene a Task Force of roughly a dozen members – including experts from outside the Arctic research community – with relevant expertise. The composition and specific tasks of this group are outlined in more detailed in Section 3 of this proposal. Building on initial exchange through e-meetings and other means of communication, a workshop in Fall 2009 would lay out a strategy for choosing the most promising approaches and methods for Arctic observing system design and optimization. These activities constitute Phase I of the ADI process. The group would define a set of specific tasks, such as proof-of-concept activities, that would be taken up by individual PI's or small PI groups in Phase II of the ADI process. These tasks would have to be performed in a short period of time so that their results could inform the immediate next steps in the development of the Arctic observing system. The results would inform a second workshop in spring 2010 that would evaluate these and other relevant efforts. Phase II of the ADI process would then conclude with completion of a report summarizing findings and recommendations that would form the foundation for further future efforts (such as future calls for proposals, coordination of activities etc.). The report should in particular provide guidance to NSF on the design, implementation and longer-term perspective of an Arctic observing system. The observing system design would not only be informed by data from instrumental records and models, but would also utilize paleo-data to place the present changes into the proper historical context and strengthen the attribution studies.

(3) Synthesis and discussion of design options and approaches as part of the AON PI Meeting, fall 2009

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The AON PI Meeting offers an opportunity to synthesize ongoing activities reported at the level of themes or disciplines rather than individual projects, with invitees from within and outside of SEARCH to provide such broader-scale evaluations. The participation of AON PIs who have spent significant time and effort on the (mostly) disciplinary and region-specific aspects of an AON would allow for productive discussion of these synthesis talks. Participating members from the AON program, the SEARCH SSC, OCP and UCP would provide perspectives on system design approaches in the context of SEARCH. Agency personnel involved in observation programs, such as the Dept. of Interior's Regional Climate Monitoring Network design team, could provide input on interagency coordination aspects where needed. Furthermore, experts with a perspective on the international observing system landscape (e.g., DAMOCLES, ArcticNet and Asian programs) could provide input on pan-Arctic coordination. Holding the AON PI Meeting in conjunction with the first ADI Task Force Workshop would ensure effective meeting flow, also from the perspective of introducing and informing Task Force members of ongoing activities.

(4) White paper on Arctic observing system design

A more fundamental examination of the design philosophies, options and challenges for a comprehensive AON may require the form of a white paper that draws on, but goes well beyond efforts currently underway at the disciplinary or project-level (Fig. 1). Such a white paper may draw on existing efforts at identifying needs and approaches towards observing system implementation, such as the white paper prepared for the OceanObs 2009 Symposium or the reports put together for the Arctic Council's Snow, Water, Ice and Permafrost in the Arctic Assessment. The group working on such a white paper would comprise a small but balanced mix of Arctic experts and potential contributors from outside of the polar community. The paper would address in particular those aspects unique to the AON and try to map out the fundamental aspects of a design and implementation strategy that successfully addresses the challenges outlined above. The paper would serve as a discussion item and potential contribution to the deliberations by the Task Force.

Additional considerations: Interagency coordination and guidance on societal information needs

An AON that is embedded in SEARCH as an interagency effort will require effective and far-reaching coordination among different agencies involved in Arctic observation programs. Some agencies also have resources and expertise pertaining to design of observing systems at lower latitudes that may be of relevance. Identifying and cultivating effective means of coordination will require a dedicated effort, including key contacts for AON design and implementation discussions within different agencies and – to insure resources for coordination efforts - involvement of agency representatives at higher levels. The Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC) and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) can provide crucial guidance and help facilitate such efforts and should be kept apprised of ADI Task Force activities. A key aspect of the SEARCH program is the integration of activities that address the observation, understanding and response to Arctic environmental change. Hence, even in a quantitative, scientifically driven effort at observatory system design, guidance on the

societal information needs component of an observing system will be critical. In order to help with this task, key experts should contribute to the different activities outlined above. In particular, stakeholders and governments have needs for data at unique spatial and temporal scales relevant to human activities.

3. Task Force Composition

In order to be successful, the ADI Task Force members need to represent a good balance between Arctic researchers and observing system design experts from other fields outside of the Arctic. The latter should represent expertise on observing system design covering a broad range of approaches, including methods other than OSSEs. While representation of key disciplines is important, it is also recognized that the currently funded AON projects reflect the broadly recognized notion that changes in the Arctic Ocean – sea ice – atmosphere system are of particular importance and urgency in understanding and responding to Arctic change (Serreze et al., 2007; Brigham, 2007; Jia et al., 2003; Overland et al., 2008; Burn and Zhang, 2009). In order to be effective, the Core Task Force will have to be manageable in size, i.e., around a dozen individuals, but will be able to draw in much broader expertise for the two ADI workshops and the report from a group of an additional 20 to 30 individuals discussed further below. Membership of the core Task Force is also driven by the ability to work well in the highly interdisciplinary and diverse setting represented by this group.

Based on these considerations, the following individuals are tentatively identified as members of the core Task Force:

- (1) Peter Schlosser, Columbia University, global tracer oceanography, outgoing Chair, SEARCH SSC
- (2) Hajo Eicken, University of Alaska Fairbanks, sea ice geophysics, incoming Chair, SEARCH SSC, outgoing Chair SEARCH OCP,
- (3) John Walsh, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Arctic atmosphere, ocean and sea-ice climatology and dynamics, SEARCH UCP Chair,
- (4) Craig Lee, University of Washington, autonomous underwater vehicles and sensor networks, physical oceanography, incoming SEARCH OCP Co-Chair,
- (5) Mark Serreze, National Snow and Ice Data Center, Arctic climate, data management and dissemination, ARCSS Committee and UCP member,
- (6) Larry Hamilton, University of New Hampshire
- (7) Charles Vörösmarty, City University of New York, Director of Environmental Cross-Roads Initiative, hydrology and water use; or Jim McNamara, Boise State University, hydrological field program design
- (8) Mohan Ramamurthy, NCAR, Director of Unidata, data assimilation, cyberinfrastructure and related tools,
- (9) John Vandecastle, University of New Mexico, technology and remote sensing in terrestrial ecology, Associate Director (Technology) for Long-term Ecological Research (LTER) program
- (10) Sandy Andelman, Conservation International, Director for Center for Applied Biodiversity Science, terrestrial ecology and sensor network design

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(11) Thomas Kaminski, FastOpt-Hamburg/Germany, inverse modeling and climate sensor network design

(12) Marika Holland, NCAR, general circulation models and atmosphere-ice-ocean interaction

(13) N.N., network design for the Global Ocean Observing System

(14) N.N., array design expert, Tropical Atmosphere Ocean Project

The task force will be augmented by a member of the SEARCH Project Office (SPO) to ensure continuity within the SEARCH process and provide support in meeting the Task Force's objectives and deliverables. The broader group to be involved in the workshops and report writing, would include experts filling gaps not addressed by the core Task Force, such as members of the Arctic research community knowledgeable in OSSEs and related efforts (D. Bromwich, A. Proshutinsky), experts on assimilation in sea ice modeling and placement of moorings (R. Lindsay), experts in design of coastal or Arctic terrestrial monitoring sites, researchers or stakeholder representatives familiar with adaptation to environmental and socio-economic change and others.

4. ADI Phase I: The Need for a Fall ADI Workshop, Scope and Planning of Activities

While some of the Task Force activities can be accomplished outside of in-person meetings, there is an urgent need for the workshop outlined in Section 2 (# 2) above. There have been meetings in the past discussing the broader implementation and general design of the AON, notably the SEARCH Implementation Workshop in 2005 and the Arctic Observation Integrations Workshops in 2008. However, at this point there has not been a meeting (or other activity) discussing design and implementation of an AON at the level of specificity outlined above. Moreover, so far the discourse has mostly been within the Arctic research community; this meeting would be the first to have dedicated involvement from experts outside of the Arctic, with significant benefits to be derived for the broader Arctic research community and strengthening of those aspects of SEARCH focusing on low-high latitude linkages.

The Task Force will determine the content and flow of the ADI Workshops, however, a rough outline of a potential agenda for the first of these in the Fall of 2009 (for which funds are sought through this proposal and a parallel request by the Joint Office of Science Support, JOSS, at the National Center for Atmospheric Research, NCAR) includes the following:

- Introduction to SEARCH/AON, expectations from NSF, overview of the Task Force charge
- Brief review of SEARCH science questions (as updated by UCP, see Section 2, #1 above) and AON implementation status (summarizing results from AON PI meeting, see Section 2, #3 above)
- Definition of the problem and task at hand
- Examples of successfully implemented observation networks, lessons learned as applicable to AON: LTER, TAO, etc.
- Review of challenges specific to AON

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- Review of principal approaches, methods and tools relevant for observing system design and implementation
- Discussion of next steps: Proof-of-concept, exploratory studies
- Discussion of next steps: Other activities and planning of report
- Workshop conclusions and recommendations

Workshop participants would be the members of the Task Force and another 15 to 25 participants representing key areas of expertise and backgrounds. An effort would be made to entrain groups underrepresented in science and engineering, including the invitation of stakeholder representatives from Arctic indigenous organizations or communities. Due to the nature of the ADI process requiring specific expertise and skills and the need for a small group that can work effectively, workshop participation would be primarily by invitation with a few slots held open for scientists who express an interest outside of the target group. As the results from the workshop and follow-up activities will be disseminated widely, this approach appears justified. The designated location for the meeting is in Boulder, Co where support from JOSS/NCAR is available and where a number of other potential participants and ADI Task Force members are located. Furthermore, funding is in place at NCAR to cover travel for the participants of the ADI workshop that do not have other appropriate sources of support. The Organizing Committee for the workshop will be constituted of the ADI Task Force Executive Committee and a few other key Task Force Members/Participants.

In order not to pre-empt deliberations and recommended plans for action by the ADI Task Force and Workshop participants, the present proposal only seeks funding support for Phase I of the ADI activities. Specifically (and as detailed in the budget explanation), the support will help the Task Force Executive Committee and a few key participants to conduct business in order to help move the process forward, which will include meetings in Boulder and Washington, DC. Once the Task Force with input from workshop participants have determined a plan of action, and following consultations with NSF and other key partners, then Phase II of the ADI process will go forward and a proposal detailing the next steps and seeking support for them will be submitted.

5. Timeline of Task Force Activities and Management Plan

Table 1 provides a list, associated timeline and responsibilities for activities that are part of the *ADI Task Force's* portfolio or that are relevant for their work. An *Executive Committee* for the ADI Task Force (with involvement by the PIs for this proposal) will be formed in order to assure that milestones and deadlines (Table 1) are met, communication with NSF is maintained, and to oversee SPO support of the ADI process. The broader group of participants in the two ADI workshops will inform and directly contribute to the deliberations and recommendations that will culminate in the report to be completed by late spring/early summer 2010.

A key aspect of the ADI process will be the completion of small-scale proof-of-concept or *exploratory studies* that will help the ADI Task Force evaluate the potential value of different approaches and methodologies. The ADI Task Force will work with Fall ADI workshop participants in identifying promising approaches and target PIs for

Appendix C: AON Design and Implementation Plan

involvement. While it is anticipated that NSF will have resources available allowing such studies recommended by the ADI Task Force to go ahead (likely at the level of c. \$20k each for between five and ten projects), it will be up to the PIs to seek funding support in a manner that would allow completion for the April 2010 deadline.

The *SEARCH Project Office* will support the ADI process and ensure continuity and tie-in into the broader array of SEARCH activities and previously established recommendations and findings. This support will take the form of help in preparing workshop agendas, facilitation of ADI activities such as identification of potential contributors (incl. outside of Arctic research community), compilation and organization of relevant documents and papers for workshops and associated work, and core support in assembling, producing and disseminating the final report. The observing system design report would address coordination and buy-in from governments at multiple levels (national, regional, local, indigenous peoples' organizations, etc.) with respect to collecting and sharing data with the scientific community; the SPO would help ensure that these groups are aware of the ADI process and report.

The Fall ADI Workshop will receive organizational support at the local level (Boulder) by the *JOSS/NCAR support group*. This support would include the following: arrangements for workshop venue and meals, arrangements for audio-visual support incl. computer and network access, processing of travel-related expenses and booking of flights and accommodations for participants not already covered through other arrangements (e.g., AON PI Meeting), communication with workshop participants in regards to workshop logistics, maintenance of web site with meeting logistics information. JOSS/NCAR would also support travel costs for an estimated 25 ADI workshop participants that do not have other sources of funding support.

Table 1: Timeline of ADI process and Task Force activities

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Lead</i>	<i>Time period</i>
Assess state of AON implementation relative to SEARCH/ISAC questions (incl. critical updates to SEARCH science questions)*	UCP et al. (Walsh)	June – October 2009
Planning of AON PI Mtg*	OCP (Lee & Eicken)	June-October 2009
Identify potential members of ADI Task Force*	Eicken, Schlosser, Walsh	July-August 2009
Task Force initiates ADI process, plans ADI Fall workshop*	Eicken, Schlosser, Walsh	August-October 2009
Assemble small team for observing system white paper*	Eicken, Schlosser	August 2009
ADI Task Force reviews UCP AON status document*	ADI	October 2009
AON PI Meeting	OCP & JOSS/NCAR & SPO	November 2009
Fall ADI Workshop*	ADI & JOSS/NCAR & SPO	November 2009
ADI Task Force identifies key proof-of-	ADI	November/December

Appendix C: AON Design and Implementation Plan

concept and exploratory design exercises*		2009
ADI Task Force Executive Group to visit with NSF and other programs in DC*	ADI Executive Group	December 2009/January 2010
Small ADI Task Force follow-up and planning meeting*	ADI	January-February 2010
Exploratory studies underway	Indiv. PIs	January-April 2010
White paper on observing system due ADI	Eicken, Schlosser	April 2010
ADI Task Force reviews results from exploratory studies	ADI	April/May 2010
Spring 2010 ADI Workshop	ADI & SPO & tbd	May 2010
ADI Task Forces prepares first draft of report	ADI	June 2010
Final report due at NSF	ADI	July 2010

Activities that are part of Phase I of the ADI process covered by this proposal are marked with an asterisk

6. Broader Impacts of Proposed Activities

The ADI process will help ensure that the scientific efforts associated with the AON will yield results and outcomes that are of societal relevance and in line with the nation's information needs. Several components of the ADI process and the Task Force activities are aimed at ensuring that observing system design and implementation meet the recognized needs for a network that have been identified by the scientific community and key stakeholder groups. Through involvement of experts from outside of the Arctic research community, we aim to achieve significant progress in this regard by identifying programs at lower latitudes successful at ensuring broader impacts, by strengthening the ties of Arctic research and observation programs to lower-latitude programs, and by exploring how the AON can best contribute to the challenge of designing a broadly interdisciplinary, holistic observing system as required in the Arctic. While the ADI process and Task Force involve a small group of people, the ADI activities outlined above and the final report emanating from this work will ensure that the discourse is carried beyond the scientific community to the broader community Arctic stakeholders.

7. Results From Prior NSF Support

“Collaborative Research on Long-Term Observations of the Energy and Mass Balance of Coastal Ice Covers in Northern Alaska” OPP 9910300, to T. C. Grenfell, H. Eicken, D. K. Perovich, and G. A. Maykut, 2000-2003, \$757,474. This grant supported optical, heat and mass balance studies over the predominant surface types in the sea-ice coastal zone at Barrow from 2000 to 2002. Annual mass balance, thermal structure of ice and permafrost

Appendix C: AON Design and Implementation Plan

active layer, melt pond development, and evolution of optical properties of snow, ice and tundra surfaces were investigated, providing the basis for a physics-based model of the evolution of melt ponds and their albedo and for a characterization of the evolution of total and spectral albedo of coastal ice and tundra (www.arcticice.org; www.gi.alaska.edu/~eicken/he_proj/BRWICE/intro.htm). Publications from this project include *Frey et al.*, 2001; *Eicken*, 2003; *Eicken et al.*, 2004; *Grenfell and Perovich*, 2004; *Mahoney et al.*, 2003, 2004.

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ARCUS Year 3 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2010)

ARCUS Year 3 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2010)

ARCUS Year 3 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2010)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination

HBEST Science Plan: Final Editing, Publication, and Distribution

Participation in monthly BEST PI teleconferences

2.1.1. ARCSS

ARCSS Website Updates, as Needed

2.3.1 Social Sciences Coordination and 2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

2.3.1 Publish *Earth is Faster Now* Reprints

4.1. Update the *Arctic Science Discoveries* Poster

ARCUS Year 3 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2010)

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

← Extreme Cold Weather Gear Kit, Educator Travel Scholarships, Polar Education Mailing List →

← Other arctic science education and outreach activities, to be determined with the program officer as opportunities arise. →

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

← Ongoing Tour Management (6 In-person and 2 Online Tours) →

ARCUS Year 3 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2010)

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

5. CORE SUPPORT

ARCUS Cooperative Agreement Tentative Staffing Plan: 2010 (Year 3)

Staffing plan is tentative and subject to personnel changes, changes in CA activities, and other staffing decisions. Staff listed first under each task are generally considered "lead staff" for that task. The "non-lead" staff listed vary in level of participation in tasks and may represent very minor time (as low as 6-8 hours of time total), but those staff are still included to give a sense of project teams and various duties.

1.1 SEARCH Coordination

Staff	Position	Project Role
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Oversight and general direction of SEARCH activities
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Participation in SEARCH activities, management
Reija Shnoro	Project Manager	SSC management, international SEARCH activities, logistics and meeting arrangements
Judy Fahnestock	Project Assistant	General SEARCH support; Understanding Task Force Activities
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Minor time for logistics/travel arrangement support
Zeb Polly	System Administrator	Minor time for IT support for website

1.2 Arctic Data Coordination

No activities planned.

1.3 State of the Arctic Conference

Staff	Position	Project Role
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Conference planning, overall management
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Agenda and speaker management
Reija Shnoro	Project Manager	Venue, hotel, logistics lead, Organizing Committee support
Judy Fahnestock	Project Assistant	Overall conference planning, abstract submission/organization, press/media
Zeb Polly	System Administrator	IT/ technical website development, outreach material design
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Development of website functions (registration pages, etc)
Janet Warburton	Education Project Manager	Minor assistance with education linkages
Kristin Timm	Education Project Manager	Minor assistance with education linkages
Joed Polly	Video/Graphics Specialist	Minor time for outreach and communication resources
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Logistics arrangement support; education and outreach
Kristina Creek	Executive Assistant	Onsite assistance, poster session management

2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination

Staff	Position	Project Role
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Oversight and general management of ARCSS activities
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Minor assistance for ARCSS website

2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination

Staff	Position	Project Role
TBD		
Reija Shnoro	Project Manager	Minor logistics coordination and travel planning
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for participation/management in activities
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for overall program guidance
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Minor assistance for website

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination

No activities planned.

2.4.1 Arctic Division Science Materials		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Zeb Polly	System Administrator and Graphics	Overall design and production of Arctic Discoveries poster
Kristin Timm	Education Project Manager	Minor assistance with content and graphics
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for content guidance
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for content guidance
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Kristin Timm	Education Project Manager	Lead project management
Janet Warburton	Education Project Manager	Assistance with management of activities
Reija Shnoro	Project Manager	Logistics coordination and travel planning
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Minor website updates
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Lead project management
Reija Shnoro	Project Manager	Minor logistics coordination and travel planning for tours
Joed Polly	Video/Graphics Specialist	Minor time for editing AVS tour videos
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for programmatic guidance
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter		
Staff	Position	Project Role
TBD		
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Programmatic guidance and editorial input
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Database management of online version(s)
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Mailing, subscriber assistance
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for programmatic guidance
4.2 Website and Internet Resources		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Website maintenance, development, database management
Zeb Polly	System Administrator and Graphics	Website maintenance, networking, software/hardware
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Programmatic guidance and content development
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Overall management
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserve		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Kristina Creek	Executive Assistant	Lead project management, editing and posting announcements
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Subscriber tracking, management
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for programmatic guidance
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Kristina Creek	Executive Assistant	Lead project management
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Minor project assistance
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Website maintenance, development, database management
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for programmatic guidance

4.5 Internet Media Archive		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Joed Polly	Video/Graphics Specialist	Lead project management
Zeb Polly	System Administrator and Graphics	Minor time for IT/database support
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Minor time for programmatic guidance
Ronnie Owens	Web Developer	Minor time for website development, database management
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Kristina Creek	Executive Assistant	Project management, general community outreach support
Judy Fahnestock	Project Assistant	General community outreach support
Reija Shnoro	Project Manager	Logistics coordination
Kristin Timm	Education Project Manager	Minor assistance with educational-focused activities
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Outreach assistance
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Programmatic guidance, lead for specific activities
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Programmatic guidance, lead for specific activities
4.7 IARPC IPY Report		
Staff	Position	Project Role
TBD		
5.1 Core Support		
Staff	Position	Project Role
Susan Fox	Executive Director	Core support for programmatic activities
Helen Wiggins	Director of Programs	Core support for programmatic activities
Zeb Polly	System Administrator and Graphics	Overall IT, network, software and hardware support for CA programs
Kristina Creek	Executive Assistant	Assistance for core support - programmatic, logistics activities
Julie Griswold	Project Manager	Assistance for core support - programmatic, logistics activities

Summary of Proposed Funding 11/23/09 15:29	2008 9-month year) TOTAL	2009 YEAR 2	2009 - YEAR 2 ACTUAL &	2009 - YEAR 2 BALANCE	2010
	ACTUAL	BUDGET	FORECAST	REMAINING	YEAR 3
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 SEARCH Coordination	206,572	322,656	250,209	72,447	380,066
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination	10,196	20,237	11,734	8,503	-
1.3 State of the Arctic	-	273,245	175,131	98,114	365,009
Subtotal Direct Costs	216,768	616,137	437,074	179,063	745,074
Indirect Costs	82,398	234,132	150,129	84,003	306,822
	299,166	850,269	587,203	263,066	1,051,896
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION					
2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination					
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination	143,922	157,387	77,475	79,912	24,607
				-	
2.2 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination					
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination	12,801	58,257	23,272	34,985	52,703
				-	
2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination					
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination	-	6,000	6,100	(100)	-
				-	
2.4 Arctic Section Science Materials					
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	-	7,861	1,000	6,861	8,123
				-	
Subtotal Direct Costs	156,723	229,505	107,847	121,658	85,433
Indirect Costs	21,117	84,948	16,055	68,893	35,181
	177,840	314,453	123,902	190,551	120,615
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	24,763	19,622	18,953	669	35,348
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	5,454	25,309	11,459	13,850	33,670
Subtotal Direct Costs	30,217	44,932	30,412	14,520	69,019
Indirect Costs	11,482	17,075	10,796	6,279	28,423
	41,699	62,006	41,208	20,798	97,442
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH					
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	36,861	83,127	74,178	8,949	59,411
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	108,974	131,221	64,202	67,019	116,243
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver	14,334	24,014	34,608	(10,594)	26,925
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	1,002	13,873	7,407	6,466	14,895
4.5 Internet Media Archive	7,087	37,510	25,471	12,039	38,614
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach	235,776	91,484	91,484	0	88,327
Subtotal Direct Costs	404,034	381,228	297,350	83,878	344,415
Indirect Costs	153,533	144,866	106,913	37,953	141,829
	557,567	526,094	404,263	121,831	486,244
5. CORE SUPPORT					
5.1 Core Support	231,553	247,387	183,942	63,445	191,635
Subtotal Direct Costs	231,553	247,387	183,942	63,445	191,635
Indirect Costs	87,990	94,007	69,898	24,109	78,915
	319,543	341,394	253,840	87,554	270,550
				-	
				-	
Total Direct Costs	1,039,408	1,519,192	1,056,628	462,564	1,435,576
Total Indirect Costs	356,406	575,030	353,792	221,238	591,171
TOTAL	1,395,815	2,094,221	1,410,420	683,801	2,026,742
	NSF CA-approved:	2,085,941		Yr 3 Budget	2,026,742
	NSF supplement	8,280		Balance YR 2	(683,801)
	TOTAL YR 2 =	2,094,221		SOA Budget 2010	(497,873)
				FUNDING REQUEST	845,068

ATTACHMENT A

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.					
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009	2009 - YEAR 2	2009 - YEAR 2	2010
	year)	YEAR 2	ACTUAL &	BALANCE	YEAR 3
	TOTAL	BUDGET	FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET
	ACTUAL				
I. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 SEARCH Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	79,569	95,144	163,278	(68,134)	176,807
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	22,219	31,200	25,682	5,518	21,900
Participant Support Costs	54,964	139,912	41,493	98,419	138,959
Materials and Supplies	161	2,000	-	2,000	1,000
Publications/Dissemination	3,153	7,400	149	7,251	2,400
Consulting	3,050	5,000	2,785	2,215	4,000
Computer Services	2,578	4,000	1,682	2,318	2,000
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	40,878	38,000	15,140	22,860	33,000
Total direct costs	206,572	322,656	250,209	72,447	380,066
Total indirect costs	78,524	122,609	87,480	35,129	156,511
	285,095	445,265	337,689	107,576	536,577
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,189	7,107	1,424	5,683	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,007	2,600	(1,538)	4,138	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	80	-	80	-
Publications/Dissemination	75	450	-	450	-
Consulting	1,500	10,000	12,000	(2,000)	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	425	-	(152)	152	-
Total direct costs	10,196	20,237	11,734	8,503	-
Total indirect costs	3,874	7,690	(101)	7,791	-
	14,070	27,927	11,633	16,294	-
1.3 State of the Arctic					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	202,545	156,997	45,548	151,534
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	5,200	3,249	1,951	43,388
Participant Support Costs	-	36,000	-	36,000	32,587
Materials and Supplies	-	8,000	-	8,000	2,000
Publications/Dissemination	-	5,500	-	5,500	23,500
Consulting	-	15,000	10,259	4,741	25,000
Computer Services	-	5,000	653	4,347	1,000
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	(4,000)	3,973	(7,973)	86,000
Total direct costs	-	273,245	175,131	98,114	365,009
Total indirect costs	-	103,833	62,750	41,083	150,311
TOTAL FOR SOA	-	377,077	237,881	139,196	515,319
Subtotal Direct Community Science Planning	216,768	616,137	437,074	179,063	745,074
Subtotal Indirect	82,398	234,132	150,129	84,003	306,822
Total Community Science Planning	299,166	850,269	587,203	263,066	1,051,896
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION					
2.1 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION					
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,245	62,004	46,022	15,982	22,607
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,851	5,200	2,584	2,616	-
Participant Support Costs	6,734	67,965	1,290	66,675	-
Materials and Supplies	69	200	-	200	-
Publications/Dissemination	10	160	-	160	-
Consulting	-	1,200	-	1,200	-
Computer Services	5,156	3,000	1,280	1,720	500
Subawards	101,148	5,958	25,596	(19,638)	-
Other Direct Costs	13,709	11,700	703	10,997	1,500
Total direct costs	143,922	157,387	77,475	79,912	24,607
Total indirect costs	16,254	57,543	10,594	46,949	10,133
	160,176	214,930	88,069	126,861	34,741

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.					
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009	2009 - YEAR 2	2009 - YEAR 2	2010
	year)	YEAR 2	ACTUAL &	BALANCE	YEAR 3
	TOTAL	BUDGET	FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET
	ACTUAL				
2.2 ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION					
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,632	17,011	17,220	(209)	23,090
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	989	2,600	432	2,168	2,738
Participant Support Costs	8,429	22,386	5,012	17,374	21,616
Materials and Supplies	69	160	-	160	160
Publications/Dissemination	10	15,000	-	15,000	1,000
Consulting	-	-	-	-	4,000
Computer Services	-	1,000	431	569	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	672	100	177	(77)	100
Total direct costs	12,801	58,257	23,272	34,985	52,703
Total indirect costs	4,864	22,138	3,143	18,995	21,703
	17,665	80,395	26,415	53,980	74,406
2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION					
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	138	238	(100)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	5,308	5,308	-	-
Consulting	-	554	554	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	6,000	6,100	(100)	-
Total indirect costs	-	2,280	2,318	(38)	-
	-	8,280	8,418	(138)	-
2.4 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS					
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	7,461	-	7,461	7,723
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	400	-	400	400
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	1,000	(1,000)	-
Total direct costs	-	7,861	1,000	6,861	8,123
Total indirect costs	-	2,987	-	2,987	3,345
	-	10,848	1,000	9,848	11,468
Subtotal Direct Costs Arctic Sciences Section	156,723	229,505	107,847	121,658	85,433
Subtotal Indirect Costs	21,117	84,948	16,055	68,893	35,181
Total Arctic Sciences Section	177,840	314,453	123,902	190,551	120,615
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,790	12,879	10,453	2,426	19,759
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,763	-	6,847	(6,847)	5,475
Participant Support Costs	5,556	2,798	(168)	2,966	9,264
Materials and Supplies	-	150	-	150	150
Publications/Dissemination	953	20	-	20	100
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	3,375	1,415	1,960	500
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,701	400	406	(6)	100
Total direct costs	24,763	19,622	18,953	669	35,348
Total indirect cost	9,410	7,456	7,202	254	14,556
	34,173	27,079	26,155	924	49,905

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.						
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009	2009 - YEAR 2	2009 - YEAR 2	2010	
	year)	YEAR 2	ACTUAL &	BALANCE	YEAR 3	
	TOTAL	YEAR 2	ACTUAL &	BALANCE	YEAR 3	
	ACTUAL	BUDGET	FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET	
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,002	13,873	7,407	6,466	14,895	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	
Total direct costs	1,002	13,873	7,407	6,466	14,895	
Total indirect costs	381	5,272	2,815	2,457	6,134	
	1,383	19,145	10,222	8,923	21,028	
4.5 Internet Media Archive						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,037	37,310	25,471	11,839	38,614	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	
Publications/Dissemination	-	200	-	200	-	
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	50	-	-	-	-	
Total direct costs	7,087	37,510	25,471	12,039	38,614	
Total indirect costs	2,693	14,254	9,679	4,575	15,901	
	9,780	51,763	35,150	16,613	54,515	
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	83,312	36,383	36,383	0	53,840	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	33,341	13,000	13,000	-	13,688	
Participant Support Costs	44,304	-	-	-	-	
Materials and Supplies	316	100	100	-	200	
Publications/Dissemination	13,321	24,000	12,775	11,225	600	
Consulting	1,250	-	11,225	(11,225)	-	
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	59,932	18,000	18,000	-	20,000	
Total direct costs	235,776	91,484	91,484	0	88,328	
Total indirect costs	89,595	34,764	30,584	4,180	36,373	
	325,371	126,247	122,067	4,180	124,701	
Subtotal Direct Information and Outreach	404,034	381,228	297,350	83,878	344,415	
Subtotal Indirect	153,533	144,866	106,913	37,953	141,829	
Total Information and Outreach	557,567	526,094	404,263	121,831	486,244	
5. CORE SUPPORT						
5.1 Core Support						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	108,045	164,841	132,181	32,660	141,159	
Permanent Equipment	20,800	-	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic/foreign)	359	7,800	5,725	2,075	5,475	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	558	(558)	-	
Materials and supplies	21,341	45,500	5,356	40,144	43,000	
Publications/Dissemination	1,288	4,820	20	4,800	500	
Consulting	19,450	7,000	5,100	1,900	1,000	
Computer Services	42,689	3,375	32,524	(29,149)	-	
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	17,581	14,050	2,478	11,572	500	
Total direct costs	231,553	247,387	183,942	63,445	191,635	
Total indirect costs	87,990	94,007	69,898	24,109	78,915	
Total Core Support	319,543	341,394	253,840	87,554	270,551	
Total Direct Costs all tasks	1,039,408	1,519,192	1,056,628	462,564	1,435,576	
Total Indirect Costs all tasks	356,406	575,030	353,792	221,238	591,171	
Total All Tasks:	1,395,815	2,094,221	1,410,420	683,801	2,026,747	
				Yr 3 Budget	2,026,742	
	NSF CA-approved	2,085,941		Balance YR 2	(683,801)	
	NSF supplement	8,280		SOA Budget 2010	(497,873)	
	TOTAL YR 2 =	2,094,221		FUNDING REQUEST	845,068	
ATTACHMENT B						

FOR NSF USE ONLY

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)			PROPOSAL NO.		DURATION (MONTHS)	
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/PROJECT DIRECTOR			AWARD NO.		Proposed	Granted
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PIs, Faculty and Other Senior Associates List each separately with name and title. (A.7. Show number in brackets)			NSF-Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By Proposer	Funds Granted by NSF (If Different)
			CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1. Executive Director – Susan Fox			9			106,720 \$
2. Director of Programs – Helen Wiggins			11			105,000
3.						
4.						
5.						
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET EXPLANATION PAGE)						
7. (2) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1-6)						211,720
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)						
1. () POSTDOCTORAL ASSOCIATES						
2. (9) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)			61			305,095
3. (1) GRADUATE STUDENTS						28,886
4. () UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS						
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)						51,878
6. () OTHER						
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)						597,579
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)						227,080
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)						824,662
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)						
TOTAL EQUIPMENT						
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)						98,138
2. FOREIGN						
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT						
1. STIPENDS \$ 6,400						
2. TRAVEL 75,000						
3. SUBSISTENCE 137,866						
4. OTHER -0-						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (54)			TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS			219,266
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS						
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES						46,610
2. PUBLICATION/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION						29,700
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES						72,000
4. COMPUTER SERVICES						4,000
5. SUBAWARDS						-0-
6. OTHER						141,200
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS						293,510
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)						1,435,576
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A) (SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) 41.18% on H – G5						
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)						591,171
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)						2,026,742
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECT SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)+ Amend #3						1,181,674
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)						845,068 \$
M. COST SHARING: PROPOSED LEVEL \$			AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT: \$			
PI/PD TYPED NAME AND SIGNATURE*			DATE		FOR NSF USE ONLY	
Susan E. Fox						
			11/23/09			
			INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			

ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*

DATE

Date Checked

Date of Rate Sheet

Initials-ORG

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*SIGNATURES REQUIRED ONLY FOR REVISED BUDGET (GPG III.C)

*K. RESIDUAL FUNDS: Inclusive of Amendment #3 of CA0618885 already funded \$497,873 and residual funds from 2009 for further support of 2010 projects \$683,801 = \$1,181,674

ATTACHMENT D